

Residual Constraint Approach (RCA): Framework & Protocol

An updated version of the paper originally published on Zenodo, March 5, 2025.

William Bert Craytor, SRA

Vol. 1, Issue 1 · Summer 2026

Published July 1, 2026

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.14787917](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14787917)

© 2026 William Bert Craytor. Published by Pacific Vista Net.

This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).

Abstract. A significant limitation of conventional appraisal methods is their reliance on outdated manual techniques, such as matched pair analyses, which bypass property feature value contributions as if they didn't exist: the traditional sales grid has no column for value contributions, only adjustments. In fact, value contributions provide the necessary basis for mathematical constraints that prevent over and undervaluation by traditional appraisers.

The Residual Constraint Approach (RCA) advances the traditional Sales Comparison Approach (SCA) by integrating a multi-phase valuation process that employs Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS) alongside rigorous mathematical constraints on feature value contributions, in particular unmeasured features — latent variables such as aesthetics, design, condition and quality — whose values are typically subject to subjective judgment and bias by the traditional appraiser.

The mathematical constraints in RCA rely on the expert application of MARS regression to estimate the value contributions of measurable property features to the sale price. However, this estimate typically accounts for only about 80% of the actual sale price, excluding subjectively assessed features like design, functional utility, condition, and quality. In the San Francisco Bay Area, the residual—representing these subjective components—averages around 20% of the total property value. The 80/20 figure reflects the author's experience in the San Francisco Bay Area under typical data conditions and should not be read as a market-invariant constant. In markets where the achievable R^2 is lower, the framework's response is to identify and measure unmeasured value drivers — distance to the ocean in coastal communities, elevation in hillside neighborhoods, and similar variables collected from external sources when MLS data does not supply them — rather than to accept the limitation and report wider error bands. While MARS residuals are often treated as estimation errors in other contexts, in real estate valuation they serve as an indirect measure of latent variable value. Though this might initially seem impractical, proof demonstrates that the residual can be meaningfully decomposed into descriptive components, provided their contributions sum to the residual—without affecting the final valuation outcome.

This methodology emerges from two decades of empirical application by the author, developed through iterative MARS implementations in R and Python environments.

Keywords: real estate valuation, residential appraisal, Residual Constraint Approach, MARS, multivariate adaptive regression splines, sales comparison approach, residual analysis, latent variables, automated valuation

Contents

[1 Introduction](#)

2	Background	6
3	Valuation Engineer	8
4	Assumptions	9
5	RCA Workflow	11
5.1	Types of MARS Analysis	11
5.2	Processing Workflow	11
5.3	Data Workflow	12
5.3.1	Data Requirements for MARS	13
5.3.2	Protocols: Closed Sales Listings	14
5.4	Project Folder Structure	16
5.4.1	Protocols: Multiple MARS (earth) Runs	17
5.5	The Core Excel Workbook	19
5.6	Backups	19
6	Workbook Notation	20
6.1	Descriptive Dimensions	20
6.1.1	The Project Dimension (“a”)	21
6.1.2	Run Version Dimension (“r”)	22
6.1.3	Workflow Stages (“w”)	22
6.1.4	Excel Workbook Sheets (“s”)	22
6.1.5	Property Listings (“p”) - MLSData rows	23
6.1.6	MLS Variables (“v”) MLSData Columns	23
6.1.7	Final Notation Example	24
6.1.8	Justification	24
6.1.9	Matrices?	25
6.1.10	First Simplification	25
6.1.11	Second Simplification	25
7	The RCA Sales Grid	27
8	Variables	30
8.1	Variable Origin Ontology	30
8.2	Variable Application Ontology	31
8.3	Second- and Third-Degree Terms	32
8.3.1	Adjustment Variables	33
8.3.2	Aggregation Variables	33

8.3.3	Special Variables & Notation	34
8.3.4	Breaking Down Residuals	34
9	Core RCA Proofs	36
10	MARS Model	37
10.1	Model Variable and Interaction “ <i>g</i> ” Functions	37
10.2	Indexing of the <i>g</i> Functions	37
10.3	Graphing Dimensions	38
10.4	The Final Model Equation	38
10.5	Number of Charts Needed to Graph a Model	39
11	Data Characteristics	42
11.1	Purpose of the Residual	42
11.2	Condition and Quality Ratings as Approximate Regressors	43
11.3	Data Errors	43
11.4	What Is Accuracy?	44
11.5	The Subject Property As An Anomaly	46
11.6	The CVR2’s Importance In Dealing With Unexpected Data	46
12	Residuals	48
12.1	Ranking & Scoring	48
12.2	CQA-Residual Curve	51
12.3	The CQA Curve Characteristics	51
12.3.1	Analysis of the CQA Curve Components	51
12.3.2	Market Dynamics and Social Implications	52
12.4	Subject Residual	52
12.5	RCA Value Conclusion	54
12.5.1	General Considerations	54
12.5.2	Review, Auditing, Complaints	54
13	Conclusion	56

1 Introduction

This paper presents the logical and mathematical foundation for a modern approach to accurately estimating the market value of residential and other real estate properties. The method, developed over 20 years of experience applying Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines (MARS) software to Northern California homes — particularly in San Francisco Bay Area communities — offers a significant advancement in valuation precision. MARS enhances valuation quality by

adeptly capturing non-linear relationships between property features and value, while efficiently identifying and prioritizing the most impactful variables. This capability allows appraisers to uncover value dynamics in new market areas far more rapidly than traditional methods permit. MARS forms the backbone of the proposed Residual Constraint Approach (RCA). The RCA method earns its name through its rigorous framework:

- It imposes strict constraints on value contributions from both measured and unmeasured property features:
 1. All MARS-derived value contributions, including the residual, must sum to the net sale price of each comparable property.
 2. The residual may be decomposed into sub-components with assigned values, provided their total equals the comparable's residual.
- RCA minimizes bias in estimating subjective features — such as aesthetic appeal, condition, and quality — by tying their total value to the residual, which is accurately quantified when a competent valuation engineer constructs the MARS model.

While primarily designed for residential real estate, where subjective features significantly influence market value, RCA holds potential for broader asset valuation applications. Accurate appraisals are critical given the U.S. residential real estate market's estimated \$45 trillion value. Fannie Mae notes that typical appraisals deviate by about 5% from actual sale prices, though this figure masks bias, as appraisers often face pressure to align with sale prices. Moreover, since 60%–70% of appraisals support refinancing — lacking comparable sale prices — the need for precision, as offered by RCA, becomes evident. The Federal Reserve's 2012 analysis estimated that 15%–20% of pre-2008 crisis appraisals deviated by over $\pm 10\%$ from sale prices, a range likely still relevant for refinancing appraisals today, varying by property type and market. Why does accuracy matter? For low loan-to-value (LTV) transactions — e.g., a buyer with strong credit putting \$500,000 down on a \$1 million home — lenders may waive appraisals, assuming minimal foreclosure risk. However, buyers who skip appraisals risk overpaying, discovering defects only after purchase. This underscores the value of robust valuation methods like RCA. Quantifying appraisal accuracy remains challenging. Researchers lack direct metrics for “market value” deviations, relying instead on indirect proxies. Traditional appraisal methods, rooted in subjective judgment and variable appraiser competency, complicate analysis. Strategies include:

1. Tzioumis (2016) studied 4,782 appraisers across 259,436 appraisals in 11 states, finding one-third within 1% of contract price, half between 1%–3% above, and a minority averaging 5% above — suggesting upward bias. The study identified two appraiser types: “at market value” (close to contract price) and “above market value” (consistently higher).
2. Krivorotov and LaCour-Little (2020) found 90% of purchase appraisals met or exceeded contract prices, highlighting “anchor bias” — the tendency to align with a desired value — especially in refinancing contexts.

These studies reveal bias in appraisal practices, amplified by the limitations of traditional tools. If appraisers were uniformly competent and unbiased, their valuations would converge; persistent overvaluation by some groups signals systemic issues.

The bias studies cited above, and the systemic pattern they point to, reflect a deeper feature of traditional sales-comparison practice that RCA is designed to address. The traditional methodology operates on two channels with very different epistemic status. On the measurable-feature channel — GLA, room counts, lot size, age, location — the appraiser is expected to derive adjustment values objectively, through matched-pair analysis or local linear regression

on comparable sales. Competent appraisers do this work, and the resulting adjustments are at least roughly defensible against the data. Even here, though, the traditional grid records only adjustments; it does not even have a column for value contributions. Nor are traditional adjustments calculated as differences between value contributions — they are estimated directly, from matched pairs or similar procedures, without the underlying contributions ever being computed. In RCA, by contrast, every adjustment is the difference between the subject's and the comparable's value contributions for the given feature — the structure whose consequences Proof II makes precise. On the subjective-feature channel — condition, quality of construction, design, functional utility, aesthetics — the available support procedures range from thin to threadbare. Subjective-feature adjustments can be supported by matched-pair analysis of properties outside the immediate comparable set, by appeal to recognized peer practice, or by reference to the appraiser's documented experience in the market. All three are formally compliant with professional standards. None of them rises to the statistical rigor that the measurable channel achieves routinely.

The result is a procedural asymmetry between what the standards require and what the methodology can deliver. The standards require support for every adjustment, measurable or subjective. The methodology delivers robust support on one channel and a spectrum of weaker procedures on the other, ranging from an anecdotal matched pair of sample size one to a citation of what other appraisers customarily use. The honest competent appraiser doing careful matched-pair work on a view adjustment produces meaningfully better support than one citing peer practice without basis, but a reviewer comparing the two appraisals on the standard form cannot easily distinguish them, because the form records the adjustment value, not the rigor of its derivation. The methodology tolerates the asymmetry because no stronger procedure for subjective features has been generally available to working appraisers.

RCA improves both channels, but in categorically different ways. On the measurable channel, the MARS regression captures non-linear relationships, variable interactions, and basis-function structure that matched-pair analysis and ordinary linear regression cannot represent. Fit against the full set of qualified sales in the market area — typically several hundred — rather than against the three to nine comparables of the traditional grid, the MARS-derived value contributions are both objective and substantially more accurate than the methodology they replace. On the subjective channel, RCA does something different in kind from any of the traditional support procedures. It does not attempt to estimate adjustment values for individual subjective features at all. The contributions of all subjective features — latent variables — collectively appear as the residual: the difference between each comparable's actual net sale price and its MARS-predicted price, calculable from data without appraiser input. The decomposition of that residual into named components — Design, Functional Utility, View, Condition, Quality, and so on — is constrained to sum to the residual total, and by Proof II (Section 9) any decomposition satisfying that constraint yields the same value conclusion. The judgment that remains in the workflow is the placement of the subject in the ranked residual distribution of the comparables, made against an inspectable ranking and explicitly documented in the report. A weak RCA appraisal is still possible — an inexperienced VE can produce an overfit MARS model, place the subject implausibly, or miss anomalies in the data — but it is weak in ways a reviewer can identify by inspecting the model and the ranking, rather than weak in ways that a standard-form review cannot surface.

Beyond refinancing, appraisers owe owners accurate valuations, especially for high-value purchases where errors can cost tens or hundreds of thousands. Yet, many balk at spending \$600–\$1,000 on appraisals, doubting their added value. Advanced methods like RCA, while initially resource-intensive, promise greater precision. With refinement and experience, their efficiency — and adoption — should increase.

2 Background

The author's educational background is in mathematics, computer science, and statistics. By profession, he is a software engineer with secondary experience in appraisal and accounting. He has been doing appraisals, off and on, since 2002 and has applied MARS since about 2004 for determining property adjustments and price trends in residential real estate.

Appraising with MARS is "deep experience" in appraisal. MARS generates models that reflect in greater detail than any other statistical method both the variables that contribute to market value and how changes in those values impact sale price. Thus, in appraising with MARS, the appraiser is constantly investigating causal relationships between variable values and sale prices as generated by MARS models.

In the interest of transparency, the RCA methodology is best applied to residential areas with these characteristics:

1. Complex neighborhoods with properties that are quite different from one another
 - Older homes
 - Varied qualities of updating
 - Many different architectures and designs
 - Variation in property attributes like GLA, lot size, elevation, and view.
2. Complex market conditions
 - Quickly changing market conditions
 - Many different types of buyers
3. Good data sources: The RCA protocol is based on Data Mining and needs plentiful quality data. While it can be used for areas with sparse data, it might not be worth the time and cost required.
4. Accurate estimates of market value are desired. RCA should, in most cases, be able to provide $\pm 1\text{-}2\%$ accuracy. The valuation engineer report should comment on the conditions for accuracy in the final value conclusion. If data or information is lacking, or if consistent patterns in the market have not been uncovered through data mining, then the accuracy will suffer, and the client should be informed of the situation. Specifically, a high R2 and CVR2 (cross-validated R2, computed by repeatedly partitioning the MLS data set into random training and test partitions), a meaningful MARS model, and a strong pattern in property CQA (condition-quality-appeal) features in the ranked residuals are the principal means for assessing accuracy and reliability in the value conclusion.

The development of these RCA protocols over the past 20+ years is based on the availability of MLSListings Inc. (Sunnyvale, CA) and other MLS, which are currently accessible through MLSListings, which comprises over 95% of the author's data analysis experience. The author's expertise stems from extensive appraisal work across 15 primary Northern California counties, with additional experience in 10 secondary counties.

The RCA methodology is most effective in markets that meet two key criteria:

1. Rich availability of high-quality appraisal data
2. Complex, heterogeneous residential areas characterized by:

- Diverse architectural styles
- Varying degrees of property updates
- Multi-decade development patterns

California County Experience

Statements made in this paper are based on experience valuing properties in the following North California counties:

San Mateo	Santa Clara	Marin	Napa	Monterey	Santa Rosa
Alameda	San Francisco	Contra Costa	Sacramento	El Dorado	San Joaquin
Stanislaus	Placer	Solano	Mendocino	Lake	Colusa
Merced	Nevada	San Benito	Santa Cruz	Sutter	Yuba

The above areas essentially take in the Silicon Valley and its surrounding counties, extending outward into more rural areas, including the Central Valley and Sierra foothills. It should be mentioned that the author has always had access to plentiful and *relatively* accurate data compared to what many appraisers in other less developed areas in the US have at their disposal.

The MLS data used is RESO Certified, complying with the RCF (RESO Common Format). Despite RCF certification, data of usually secondary importance is sometimes missing or incorrect for some properties, either through original tax assessor or subsequent sales agent MLS input errors. Often these errors follow a pattern, such as simply not making an input if the feature doesn't exist. For example, instead of entering 0 for "carport spaces", when there is no carport, nothing is entered. In areas where carports are rare, the analyst might substitute 0 for no data, in order to get a useful adjustment for carports. While R/earth and other MARS implementations can handle missing data, it is up to the Valuation Engineer (VE) to decide on how to handle it.

MLSListings data is also available from the MLS's of some other states, from Florida to Hawaii. This can be useful for testing how well protocols and code work in different states.

3 Valuation Engineer

Definition 1: Valuation Engineer

To prevent ambiguity, The term “Valuation Engineer” (or “VE” for short) is used to denote an individual possessing the expertise of a licensed appraiser, coupled with advanced knowledge, skills, and experience in utilizing data mining, statistics, programming, detailed protocols, and artificial intelligence to ascertain the market value of complex properties. It is also important to recognize that valuation is a task that necessitates some form of licensing due to the established potential for fraud.

Lenders typically offer several valuation options:

1. Automated Valuation Models (AVMs) - lowest cost option
2. Hybrid appraisals - utilizing unlicensed inspectors with licensed appraiser oversight
3. Standard appraisals - performed by licensed appraisers

Absent from typical consideration for appraisal work are Engineer-level Appraisals. There simply aren't many appraisers around with the skill set to do these. There should be a need for them. They can provide significantly higher accuracy and nearly guarantee fairly good objectivity with the employment of RCA methodology (MARS and constraints).

For conforming properties in newer subdivisions, standard appraisals generally suffice. However, engineer valuations are recommended for older homes in areas with significant renovation history spanning 30+ years. The choice between these methods should follow a structured decision process based on property characteristics and market conditions.

4 Assumptions

Assumption 1: Geographical Area & Property Type

The scope of this paper primarily focuses on single-family homes and condominiums in California's metropolitan and urban areas. While the Sales Comparison Approach applies to other property types and geographical regions, income and cost approaches typically play a more dominant role when valuing agricultural land, multi-family properties, and commercial real estate. In such cases, the RCA approach may need modification or have limited applicability.

Assumption 2: Data Storage

CSV and Excel are heavily used by MLS systems and assumed to be the principal way to feed data to RCA programs. Although broker feeds can be used to feed data continually into SQL databases. Backup and intermediate storage often uses SQL databases and two that play big roles are the free and open source SQLite and PostgreSQL. Text or RTF files are also used for report snippets and PNG, JPG, TIFF files are used for graphics. Note that Microsoft's SQL Server is also used by many, but the free edition "SQL Server Express" is very limited (e.g. only 1 CPU Core can be used) and other versions have hefty license fees for commercial use. Real Estate databases in California can be very large and joins can be very time consuming, so a 8+ core computer with 128G of RAM can be useful for large joins. SQL databases are also important when you need to find all of the properties in an arbitrarily bounded area. So, if for example, you used Cluster Analysis to define neighborhoods, you would be inclined to use some SQL database. However, different databases have different built-in functions for handling geographic information and thus are not compatible with one another. For this set of articles on RCA, PostgreSQL will be assumed for complex SQL tasks and SQLite for simple tasks.

Assumption 3: "R/earth" Is Used For MARS processing.

Until 2017, Salford Systems' MARS software was an affordable solution at \$270 per year. However, after Minitab's acquisition of Salford Systems, MARS was bundled into their SPM package at \$16,000 annually — a price point prohibitive for most small businesses. Fortunately, the R programming language's "earth" package (Milborrow 2024a), maintained by Stephen Milborrow, has evolved to match or exceed the capabilities of Minitab's SPM MARS. The earth package offers additional advantages: it's freely available, integrates seamlessly with R's comprehensive statistical ecosystem, and can be accessed through Python using Pandas, providing excellent flexibility for different workflows. Discussions related to MARS assume the specific use of R/earth.

Assumption 4: Notation

Raw data from external sources like CSV files and Excel spreadsheets is represented using standard Latin characters. This includes Multiple Listing Service (MLS) property data, MARS (Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines) configuration settings using the R/earth package, and project-specific data. This notation extends to their corresponding data frame representations in R or Python.

When discussing *property features* and their various types and subsets, the notation shifts to Greek letters for enhanced precision and analytical clarity. While this mathematical notation may appear more rigorous, it serves a crucial purpose: distinguishing abstract property characteristics from their raw data representations. As a convention, Greek characters consistently denote property features, while Latin characters indicate spreadsheet data structures. For instance, the symbol M represents the MLS data matrix, organized with properties as rows and their corresponding features as columns.

Assumption 5: Programming Languages

In this field R and Python w/Pandas are the dominant languages, with C or C++ being used when speed is important. R/earth is itself written in R and C.

Assumption 6: Indexing

Indexing can vary across programming languages and mathematics, which can get confusing:

- Mathematics and R start indexing at 1.
- C, C#, C++, and Python start at 0.

In this paper, to keep things consistent and simple, all indexing starts at 0 (like Python or C). Here's how it works:

- For lists, matrices, or data frames:
 - Index 0 is reserved for the “subject property” (the main property being studied).
 - Example: In a table where rows are properties, row 0 is the subject property, and column 0 holds unique IDs for all properties.
 - A practical tip: Arrange properties with the subject property first (row 0), then list others from newest to oldest sale date, numbering them sequentially (0, 1, 2, etc.).
- When there's no subject property:
 - If a data structure doesn't include properties (e.g., just variables or functions), index 0 is skipped, and indexing starts at 1.
 - Special note for R users: Since R uses 1-based indexing, when coding this paper's math in R, add 1 to all indexes to adjust from 0-based to 1-based.

5 RCA Workflow

Understanding the RCA workflow is essential for effective analysis. The process follows a structured sequence of analytical tasks and decision points

5.1 Types of MARS Analysis

The workflow for MARS analysis depends on whether only a market analysis is needed or whether the valuation or appraisal of a given property is required. Note that a specific property appraisal typically requires an analysis of its market area.

- **Market Analysis:** focuses on broad areas such as counties, cities, or defined regions. This approach does not involve a specific subject property and thus requires no value conclusion. The workflow centers on model development, validation, and the generation of supporting analytics. The process concludes once the optimal model is identified and documented.
- **Single Property Analysis** encompasses all elements of market analysis plus the determination of a specific property's value. This differs fundamentally from traditional appraisal methods. In traditional approaches, value is typically derived by adjusting 3-9 comparable sales and computing a weighted average. In contrast, RCA determines value primarily through two components:
 1. The MARS model's predicted value
 2. The estimated property-specific residual (with the associated CQA score)

The Sales Grid in RCA serves primarily to explain value differences between the subject and comparables by illustrating variable contributions. A key advantage of RCA is its stability: while clients may debate comparable selection, the value conclusion remains consistent regardless of which comparables are chosen for presentation, as all sales (whether 15 or 600) are adjusted using the same model. While older sales are automatically adjusted to current market conditions, recent sales are generally preferable. The model's effectiveness in capturing price factors diminishes with temporal distance, as unmeasured market characteristics become more significant over longer periods.

5.2 Processing Workflow

The overall processing workflow can be described by these steps:

1. Scope of work.
2. Setup initial project folders and files.
3. Download MLS data. Refer to Protocols 1.1–1.3 on the number of property records needed and setting limitations on date ranges.
4. Complete configurations sheets: Regression variables, Interactions, Aggregations, Calculations.
5. Run MARS (R/earth) regression to create price model.
6. Generate property value contributions & residuals (pure residual and residual/SF) from the MARS model.

7. Rank properties by residual/SF.
8. Create CQA scores for each comparable sale.
9. Assuming a quality ranking of properties has been produced which truly represents the overall appeal of the properties, find the best position for the subject in the ranking and assign it a CQA score, by studying the overall pattern trends in the ranking.
10. Assign the corresponding residual/SF to the subject property as residual/SF · (subject) GLA.
11. **Add the MARS price estimate and assigned residual to arrive at subject value conclusion.**
12. Break down the subject residual into descriptive components and value contributions.
13. Calculate comparable model produced value contributions & adjustments, plus all subtotals and adjusted sale prices.
14. The adjusted sale prices will be equal to the subject final value conclusion.
15. Select the 6-12 most similar properties for the Sales Grid.
16. Break down the total residual amounts for the comparables into residual component value contributions, setting the residual total value to 0 after the breakdown is completed.
17. Recalculate all subtotals and sales grid comparable adjusted sale price. Check values.
18. Upload Sales Grid to Report.

Note that with RCA, the final value conclusion does NOT directly derive from the comparable values in the Sales Grid. With the RCA method, the Sales Grid becomes a tool only for explaining why properties that appear similar to the subject, sell for more or less than the final value conclusion or the subject properties appraised value. This must be viewed a different way: The subject value conclusion depends on the MARS model price estimate, and the residual estimated by the valuation engineer. But these two quantities are very dependent on all of the properties that went into the R/earth regression, which created the ranking of property residuals that determined the CQA score of the subject property thus determined its residual through placement in the ranking by the valuation engineer. The adjustments in the Sales Grid are really determined by the imposed mathematical constraints of RCA, although the residual breakdown is somewhat at the mercy of the VE, the breakdown value contribution totals must always add up to the associated residual. We know from Proof 2 that the while the actual values if the residual components may vary depending on the judgment of the VE, their totals for a given property are completely constrained and therefore will not change the adjusted sale price for the associated property, regardless of how the VE alters the residual breakdown.

5.3 Data Workflow

Note that in this paper, only a high-level workflow is presented for the RCA method. Other articles will delve into the various stages and substages of RCA analysis.

5.3.1 Data Requirements for MARS

We will need to specify a beginning date for sales transactions and an ending date based on the effective date of appraisal or valuation. This usually takes into consideration the estimated number of regression variables and interactions that will be needed for each degree of interaction over 1.

5.3.2 Protocols: Closed Sales Listings

Protocol 1.1: Determining the Number of MLS Closed Sales Listings Required

This protocol describes how to calculate the recommended minimum number of closed sales listings to input into MARS regression. You will need to make a rough estimate, to begin with, run MARS in first, second, and possibly third-degree runs to generate the initial model, and then review the number of rows according to the following rules to determine if more rows are needed. This protocol assumes the independent variables are 100% independent, which in real estate is rarely the case; for example, GLA and room counts are usually highly correlated, and GLA is also likely to show correlation with lot size. This gets into the calculation of “Degrees of Freedom (DOF).” Each truly independent variable gets one degree of freedom. But, when there are dependencies between the so-called independent variables, an accurate calculation of the DOF requires some analysis that is beyond the scope of this paper. Just keep in mind that due to likely co-linearity between variables, the estimates below are probably on the high side.

1. For first-order terms (no interactions), the ~ 15 rows per variable rule works well
2. For each allowed two-way interaction, you should add approximately 15-30 properties
3. For higher-order interactions (3+ variables), each should have 30+ properties.

However, this isn’t a hard rule. The actual number needed can depend on:

- The signal-to-noise ratio in your data
- The complexity of relationships you’re trying to model
- The variability in your response variable
- The quality of your data

Example:

So if you have:

- 10 main variables
- 5 allowed two-way interactions
- 2 allowed three-way interactions

You might calculate your minimum number of sales as:

$$\begin{aligned} N &= (10 \text{ variables} * 15 \text{ rows/variable}) + \\ &\quad (5 \text{ two-way-interactions} * 22 \text{ rows/two-way-interaction}) + \\ &\quad (2 \text{ three-way-interactions} * 30 \text{ rows/three-way-interaction}) \\ &= 320 \text{ rows} \end{aligned}$$

Alternatively, you may do the following: After running R/earth on a set of data, you can use the number of basis functions in the model, plus one as an estimate for the degrees of freedom and then take this number times 20-30 to get the number of input records needed.

Protocol 1.2: Sales Periods Should Encompass Minimal Change in Buyer Tastes

When collecting historical property data, there is no strict time limitation if changes in market preferences can be captured through appropriate variables. Consider these key points for handling architectural evolution in your market: Changes in dominant architectural styles (such as a shift from California Ranch to Mediterranean) can be modeled using:

- Subdivision identifiers
- MLS area codes
- Construction date ranges

However, if these style changes cannot be adequately captured through specific variables, you face an important constraint: while Date of Sale is typically used to adjust for market conditions, using it simultaneously to control for architectural preferences would confound these two distinct effects. In such cases, the preferred approach is to either:

1. Limit your data collection to the period after the introduction of the newer architectural style
2. Restrict your comparable selection to subdivisions sharing the same architectural style

This ensures your analysis maintains consistency in property characteristics while still allowing proper adjustment for market conditions over time. Alternatively, at least in this case, assuming you can extract the architectural style from the data, you could consider the interaction between these two variables. However, such extraction is not always possible.

Protocol 1.3: If In An Area Of Few Sales Then Do The Best You Can

When working with MARS modeling for sales data, you need approximately 15 transactions for meaningful analysis. If you have fewer sales (for example, 5 properties), you can duplicate each record twice to reach the 15-property threshold. Important considerations for this approach:

1. Use only first-degree regression to reduce over-fitting
2. Ignore or skip cross-validation since the data set is too limited
3. While MARS will likely outperform matched pairs or standard linear regression methods in this scenario, be aware that duplicating data affects the validity of uncertainty measurements and statistical significance

The best long-term solution is to expand your data-set with additional actual sales. However, if you must proceed with limited data, data duplication provides a workable temporary solution while acknowledging its statistical limitations.

5.4 Project Folder Structure

It would be a good idea to discuss project folder structure. It is a good idea to have a separate folder for Market Analyses and Single Property Appraisals. Both of these folders have a similar subfolder structure:

```

RCA_Projects/
├── MarketAnalysis/
│   ├── Burlingame_20240501/
│   ├── Pacifica_20240310/
│   ├── RedwoodCity_20240615/
│   └── ...
├── SingleFamily/
│   ├── Pacific_Rosewood_123_20240510/
│   │   ├── Code/
│   │   │   ├── R/
│   │   │   │   └── ...
│   │   │   └── Python/
│   │   │       └── ...
│   │   └── Data/
│   │       ├── MLS_Original.xlsx
│   │       ├── MLS/
│   │       │   └── VER202402510153248/
│   │       │       ├── MLS.xlsx
│   │       │       ├── MLS_Stage2.xlsx
│   │       │       ├── MLS_Stage3.xlsx
│   │       │       ├── MLS_Stage4.xlsx
│   │       │       ├── MLS_Stage5.xlsx
│   │       │       └── Documents/
│   │       │           ├── LinearModels.pdf
│   │       │           ├── Cum_Dist.pdf
│   │       │           ├── Model.txt
│   │       │           ├── PartContrib.pdf
│   │       │           ├── Pairs.pdf
│   │       │           ├── Residual1.png
│   │       │           ├── Residual2.png
│   │       │           ├── ResidualSF.png
│   │       │           ├── Rpart.pdf
│   │       │           ├── VariablesImp.pdf
│   │       │           ├── VariableVsSP.pdf
│   │       │           └── ...

```

Stage 1 processing will create the version folder with its sub-folders. It will copy the `MLS_Original.xlsx`, even though this spreadsheet *should* never change, but reflect exactly what was downloaded from the MLS as of a certain date and time; yet there is the possibility on a lengthier project that a new MLS download will be needed. Next, this stage will make a copy of the expanded `MLS.xlsx` workbook with its configuration parameters, into the version folder. There can be many version folders each created for a complete run of MARS.

Then, the following stages will generate column additions, sorting and other changes to the workbook and write an updated version as `MLS_Stage(N)` to the project data folder when the

appraisal is completed. To reiterate, the root MLS.xlsx folder is undergoing constant change, and so the version copy is an ongoing mutation of the original MLS workbook, with variable deletions and additions, plus other changes. The processing R or Python code most likely will run with input from the Data MLS.xlsx workbook. Thus we always have a copy of all the data behind each version of the RCA run.

As many versions are created as needed until it is not possible to make improvements, at which point the best version is selected as the final version. One could change the folder name by adding “_Final” to the end of it, so it is apparent when looking through the directory. Some older versions with interesting or competing models, should usually be retained. Each version folder contains a number of text, diagram and graph files that can be embedded into a report. The final MLS_Stage5.xlsx workbook contains as many sheets as necessary for the report. In particular it may have a spreadsheet for transfer to a Fannie Mae Sales Grid. It will also necessarily contain the computations or breakdown behind aggregations. This is potentially the most time-consuming part of the RCA approach - the struggle to find the perfect model in a difficult market area.

Everything needed to recreate the sales grids needs to be copied to the version folder, including the R or Python code used - if the code undergoes frequent changes.

5.4.1 Protocols: Multiple MARS (earth) Runs

Protocol 2.1: Overfitting Runs To Surgically Study Market Area Pricing Factors

During initial earth runs, overfitting should be used strategically to discover underlying price factors. For example, a market area represented by 800 sales may contain only 3 properties with workshops, and in those isolated cases the workshop may have a major impact on the final sale price. A forward-pass-only run will produce an overfitted model that shows the approximate value contribution of these workshops. However, since there are only 3 such sales out of 800, the workshop terms will be removed in the backward pass, and certainly under cross-validation. The value that the forward-only pass assigns to workshops can be written down and transferred to the latent variable analysis, to be used for any property with a workshop that appears in the Sales Grid. Such overfitted models also give detailed estimates for many other thin-data features that would be eliminated by backward-pass pruning or cross-validated runs.

Save each of these exploratory runs as its own version folder: the recorded value contributions are evidence the VE will want to cite when breaking down residuals later. Understand, of course, that the VE must ultimately rely on pruning and cross-validation to make the final model robust against properties the regression never saw — such as a subject property that appears later on. Overfitted runs are instruments for study; they are never the final model.

Protocol 2.2: Multiple Cross-Validated Runs Under Different earth() Parameters

Market areas differ in structure and size, and the VE usually needs to experiment with a series of runs: to develop an understanding of which variables impact price the most; to judge whether the existing set of measured variables does an adequate job of estimating value, or whether new data must be added (distance to water, elevation, distance to shopping centers, and so on); and to discover new kinds of interactions while disallowing others as inefficient or misleading. In the end, the VE wants a good R2 on the training data and the best possible CVR2 against the test data. Getting there may require collecting new data, improving the accuracy of existing data, or tuning the earth() parameters to the size and character of the market area (e.g., for the available degrees of freedom — see Protocol 1.1).

This is precisely why the project structure above supports many run version folders: each candidate model is preserved with its parameters and its R2/CVR2, so the trajectory across runs can be compared. A version whose R2 climbs while its CVR2 stalls or falls is fitting noise rather than market signal, and the version history is what makes that visible.

Protocol 2.3: Prolog Expansion of Remarks and Descriptive Feature Columns

Although this facility is still in a somewhat experimental phase, earthUI now ships with a built-in Prolog engine (vProlog) and uses Definite Clause Grammars (DCGs) to parse the MLS free-text columns — Public Remarks above all, but also agent remarks and comma-delimited feature lists such as room features or existing structures. The expansion turns phrases like “owned solar,” “3 car garage,” or “40x50 workshop” into ordinary feature columns that can be offered to the regression, and thin-data features recovered this way feed the latent variable analysis directly (see the later subsection on condition and quality ratings as approximate regressors; the feature itself is documented in the earthUI companion article in this issue).

Text expansion multiplies the candidate predictor set, and that necessitates multiple earth/RCA runs for testing: expanded columns must be tried in and out of the model, consolidated into derived counts or booleans where they are collinear, and checked against CVR2 to confirm they carry market signal rather than noise. Treat each such experiment as its own run version folder, exactly as in Protocols 2.1 and 2.2. And since the parsing grammar itself is under development, the VE should review extracted columns against the source text before relying on them in a model.

5.5 The Core Excel Workbook

Since most MLS services download property data to Excel CVS worksheets, Excel is probably the most convenient way to store data and various configuration parameters. There is one core Excel Workbook for each project called `MLS.xlsx`, which has one sheet called “`MLSData`”, to store the closed property sales listings that were downloaded from the MLS, as well as several configuration and parameter sheets:

```
Workbook: MLS.xlsx/  
├─ Sheet: Project Data  
├─ Sheet: MLSData  
├─ Sheet: Regression Variables  
├─ Sheet: Calculations  
├─ Sheet: Allowed Interactions  
├─ Sheet: Aggregations  
└─ Sheet: (MARS run parameters)
```

The original data is stored in a workbook named something like `MLS_Original.xlsx`. A copy should be made with a different name, let’s say “`MLS.xlsx`,” which will load into the R or Python RCA program. Both of these workbooks are stored under the Data folder. Now, the `Data/MLS.xlsx` workbook will probably go through many iterations of runs, trying different combinations of variables, MARS parameters and changes to other settings. Each iteration creates a new input/output folder named with the date and time, with the format of `VER_YYYYMMDDHHMMSS`. Each folder will have a copy of the input `MLS.xlsx` workbook and contain the generated Excel Workbooks for each of the four processing stages (Stages 2–5), as well as the output text documents, diagrams and graphs. Note that Stage 5, the final stage, may contain a number of other sheets for the report, depending on the type of client and SOW.

5.6 Backups

When writing new or modified Excel spreadsheets to the project version folders, backups can also be made to SQLite or PostgreSQL databases in the project folder. The database files are less likely to become unintentionally corrupted over in subsequent periods, through review or reference use.

6 Workbook Notation

6.1 Descriptive Dimensions

There are roughly six descriptive dimensions for a workbook “M”:

1. Appraisals “a”
2. Run Versions “r”
3. Workflow Stages “w”
4. Sheets “s”
5. Property Listing “p”
6. Variable Set “v”

So, an individual cell in a particular workbook M can be described as:

$$\begin{matrix} r_* & & a_* & & p_* \\ w_* & W & s_* & & v_* \end{matrix} \quad (1)$$

(Note: “*” means some valid index)

or:

$$\begin{matrix} r_k & & a_g & & p_i \\ w_m & W & s_h & & v_j \end{matrix} \quad \begin{matrix} i = 1, \dots, n_p \\ j = 1, \dots, n_v \\ k = 1, \dots, n_r \\ m = 1, \dots, n_m \\ g = 1, \dots, n_g \\ h = 1, \dots, n_h \end{matrix} \quad (2)$$

where:

- n_p = # of rows (depends on sheet)
- n_v = # of columns (depends on sheet)
- n_r = # of run versions
- n_m = # of workflow stages
- n_g = # of analysis projects
- n_h = # of workbook sheets

Understand that “W” references the entire Excel Workbook of six core data sheets that each have their own table, which on running the associated R or Python program are loaded into separate internal data frames. Both R and Python have internal functions that can take a name and find which row or column of the data frame belongs to. For example, if in the subscript v_j , $v = (\text{“GLA”, “LotSize”, “BathRms”, “BedRms”, } \dots)$ and $j=0$, then $v_j = \text{“GLA”}$. Either R or Python will internally be able to resolve “GLA” to the column it is stored in, which for example, might be column 15 of the associated data frame. So, in this paper we index into our name arrays, which pass a name to the running program which re-indexes that name into the actual column or row index for the internal data frame. It is a bit complicated. But to be precise, this is necessary and most convenient. It is a “separation of responsibilities” between the analyst role and the developer role; although in reality the Valuation Engineer (VE) could be performing both roles. Note that an R “data frame” is called “dataframe” in Python.

Also note that the MARS run time parameters sheet is not a dimension of W, as W relates to the version of data being input into MARS, separate from the parameters that determine how MARS/earth handles that data.

For the sake of clarity, a complex multidimensional notation for the Workbook is presented which relates more directly to the internal R or Python data frames that the data workbook sheets are loaded into. It is “heavy” notation. But when we get into proofs and so on, we throw a lot of the baggage away by making assumptions about what we are working with. Nonetheless, this notation helps get a better overview of the workflow and data from the outset.

Let’s start with notation for the set of workbooks we will be processing.

6.1.1 The Project Dimension (“a”)

Once a Scope of Work (SOW) has been approved, a project folder needs to be setup to store input and output data, including configuration parameters, output graphs, diagrams, spreadsheets and report snippets. The VE should identify all projects with a simple sequential ID, such as an integer, so that if a report should go missing, it would be obvious. If projects are canceled, then there should be a consistent means to indicate the project has been cancelled within the given project folder, but it should never be deleted. We assume project IDs start at 0 and incremented by 1, although there are other possibilities. We further assume all valid project IDs are stored in an ordered set “a” created with the processing program.

The appraisal project data is in the project worksheet of the workbook, but could also be stored in some central SQL database,

Here are the following suggested project fields:

1. Local ID: A short integer ID that is sequentially generated for the company. This would make a great primary key for storage - and could be automatically generated by the database with each successive project.
2. Global GUID: If you want, you can create a GUID (Globally Universal ID) using
<https://www.uuidgenerator.net/>
3. Property Location (Market Analysis) or Address
4. Effective Date of Appraisal
5. Date of Order
6. Date of Inspection
7. Date of Original Report
8. Date of First Updated Report
9. Date of Second Updated Report
10. Date of Third Updated Report
11. Client Name
12. Client Address
13. Lender Name
14. Lender Address
15. Owner Name
16. Owner Address
17.

Example of list of project IDs:

```
a = ("1",  
     "2",  
     "...",  
     "141",  
     "142")
```

6.1.2 Run Version Dimension (“r”)

Second in the workflow, we execute MARS regression on the input. This will likely involve several to many executions as we alter various parameters to improve the model. Each execution will create a new version folder for the output, with a name based on the date and time of execution. For example,

```
r = (“ver20241210_083124”,
     “ver20241209_151130”,
     “ver20241208_160944”)
```

```
latest_version : r1 = “ver20241210_083124”
```

Promising versions with competitive models and output, should be kept until a final version is decided upon, or perhaps longer if they have some utility. You may want to modify the version folder to indicate it is the final version, by placing “Final” at the end of the name.

6.1.3 Workflow Stages (“w”)

The RCA Workflow is separated into usually five separate stages, as listed below. Each stage must successfully complete before starting the next stage. The VE should be able to stop the processing at the end of a stage to review the results before proceeding. This is needed because market areas are fairly complex and often quite unique. Unusual problems can be encountered that take a new approach. The VE must be able to jump into R or Python code to make necessary changes and even try new approaches. And, in such cases, he may want to experiment and try different approaches requiring multiple runs of the same stage he is working on. Although, the VE should also be free to run all stages with one command, - with some caveats (e.g. 3rd Degree Aggregation must have already been determined through a previous run of Stage 2). This means that when each stage completes, it should store all of its internal data in files or databases, so that the next stage can be started as if the previous stage were still in memory, by reloading the data from the previous stage into memory.

Here are the stages:

```
w = (“stage1”, -Setup
     “stage2”, -MARS processing
     “stage3”, -Final Sales Grid
     “stage4”, -Report snippets
     “stage5”) -Review/Cleanup
```

```
stage2 : w2 = “stage2”
```

6.1.4 Excel Workbook Sheets (“s”)

In the RCA Core Excel Workbook, we have the following sheets that are each mapped into a internal data frame:

s = (“MLSData”,
 “Regression Variables”,
 “Calculations”,
 “Interactions”,
 “Aggregations 1st & 3rd Degree”,
 “Aggregations 2nd Degree”)

The reason that 2nd degree aggregations are put on a separate sheet is that they can be most easily defined with a symmetric table that shows all possible pairs of interactions, allowing the specification of an aggregation variable for each pair’s associated value contributions and adjustments to be aggregated (added) to. We couldn’t do this with 3rd degree aggregations because that would require a 3 dimensional symmetric table which is not possible in Excel. Furthermore, a 20x20x20 table would be 8,000 cells to deal with. It is easier to just list any third degree term names in the table with the 1st degree aggregations, for example:

Variable	Aggregate To
AboveGradeFinArea	GLA
BelowGradeFinArea	BGLA
UnfinArea	UBA
LotSize	LotSize
...	...
GLA__LotSize	GLA
GLA__DateOfSale	GLA
BathRms__DateOfSale	GLA
Lat__Long	Location
Lat__Long__GLA	Location
...	...

6.1.5 Property Listings (“p”) - MLSData rows

Property listings form the rows of the MLSData sheet. They are not found in the other sheets, until Stage 4, where the final report snippets are created with the final selection of comparable properties. Here is a sample list of property IDs:

p = (“MLS823211”, “MLS823456”, “MLS823542”, “MLS823721”, “...”)

6.1.6 MLS Variables (“v”) MLSData Columns

More will be said about handling variables later. Suffice it to state at this point that MLSData sheet typically has 30-40 variables of various types, but usually only 10-20 will be selected as independent variables for the MARS regression. These variable also appear in other sheets, although typically as a list of all possible variables that can be used for submission to MARS. An example of a list of variables is:

v = (“GLA”, “SalePrice”, “BedRms”, “BathRms”, “GarageSF”, “...”)

6.1.7 Final Notation Example

Lets pull the above notation into a final example. Using the above lists, let

$$\begin{matrix} r_1 \\ w_1 \end{matrix} W_{s_0}^{a_{141}} \begin{matrix} p_2 \\ v_0 \end{matrix} \quad (3)$$

Note that we are using 0 indexing here, so that the first elements of lists is assumed to have an index of 0. Python also uses 0 indexing, but R uses 1 indexing.

So, the above means that we are talking about the cell value for:

- Variable v_0 or column “GLA”
- For property p_2 or ID “MLS823542”
- Of sheet s_0 or “MLSData”
- For workflow stage w_1 or “stage2”
- Of version r_1 or
“ver20241209_151130”
- Of project a_{141} or “142”

The above notation can also then be written as:

$$\begin{matrix} \text{“ver20241209_151130”} \\ \text{“stage2”} \end{matrix} W_{\text{“MLSData”}}^{\text{“142”}} \begin{matrix} \text{“MLS823542”} \\ \text{“GLA”} \end{matrix} \quad (4)$$

6.1.8 Justification

“Why don’t we just use indexing or numbers in the notation?” We have two requirements for our notation:

1. Subsets, e.g., the analyst frequently selecting subsets of a list, such as subsets of variables, are used. For instance, there may be 35-40 variables in the MLSData sheet but only 10-20 of them are used for a given run. From one run to the next, the VE frequently changes the variables submitted to MARS/earth.
2. Iteration, e.g., $i = 1, 2, \dots, n_1$
Our algorithms, protocols, and proofs usually need to be able to iterate through all items in an ordered list, from the first to the last - or pick out some particular item.

So, we need a letter to represent the subset or list of items, and that must have another subscript that we can use to iterate over the items of the list to give is the strings that are used to index into the data frame rows or columns.

6.1.9 Matrices?

And what about the matrices of Linear Algebra? Matrices work only with numbers, either integer or real. Matrices as a data structure are supported in both R and Python. However, many of the variables we work with in MLS data are called “strings” or character data. Even if some variables are only numbers, they are often not real numbers but just names. For example, MLS Area Codes for a city may be (“660”, “661”, “662”, “663”, . . . , “672”). Earth regression allows variables to be specified as “factor” variables, in which case the numbers are treated simply as names, without any sequence. In such cases, the model produced will merely provide a value contribution for each number, rather than a function that runs over the sequence. Other examples include “C1”, . . . , “C6” for Condition and “Q1”, . . . , “Q6” for quality.

6.1.10 First Simplification

The above notation for the core Excel project workbook is nice to tie things together, but too heavy to carry around for explaining algorithms or mathematical proofs. When we are doing the tedious work, we can assume it is within the given project, version, stage and sheet. We just say what we are working with, if it is not already implicit. All we really need from the above, once we indicate what we are working with is:

$$M_{s_h}^{p_i} \quad \begin{array}{l} i = 1, 2, \dots, n_p \\ j = 1, 2, \dots, n_v \\ h = 1, 2, \dots, n_s \end{array} \quad (5)$$

where: n_p = # properties
 n_v = # input variables
 n_s = # input sheets

6.1.11 Second Simplification

It is more convenient to rename the sheets to specific kinds of data frames they support rather than use indexes. For each sheet, the rows and columns have different functionalities. So, the W set of data frames is broken up into M, V, A, I, and C data frames as follows:

$$\diamond \text{ MLS Data} \quad M_{v_j}^{p_i} = W_0^{p_i} \quad \begin{array}{l} i = 0, 1, \dots, n_p \\ j = 0, 1, \dots, n_v \end{array} \quad (6)$$

where: n_p = # properties
 n_v = # input variables

Note: Subject Is By Default Always First in Property Lists

In the “MLSData” Excel spreadsheet and associated data frame, the first row is always reserved for the subject property. It is never sorted with the other MLS properties below it. It is never entered into the MARS regression as independent data, it is entered rather as target data, or as the dependent variable. The same holds for property lists. In all property lists, the first element with index 0, is always assumed to be the subject property ID, unless stated otherwise.

Even if the task is to create a model for a market area without any subject property, the first row is nonetheless loaded with some dummy property data. This makes it far more convenient to write programs, specify algorithms, or do proofs. So, if we are using c to

represent the list of properties, c_0 is the subject property and c_i , $i = 1, \dots, n_p$ are the comparable listings that will be input to MARS/earth regression.

◇ **Regression Variable Specifications**

$$V_{s_j}^{v_i} = \prod_{j=1,2,\dots,n_s}^{i=1,2,\dots,n_v} v_i \quad (7)$$

where: $n_v = \#$ available variables
 $n_s = \#$ of specifications

Note, $n_s \leq n_v$, as we usually select a subset of available variables for input to regression.

◇ **Calculations**

$$C_{c_j}^{v_i} = \prod_{j=1,2,\dots,n_c}^{i=1,2,\dots,n_v} v_i \quad (8)$$

where: $n_v = \#$ of variables
 $n_c = \#$ of calc specs

◇ **Interactions**

$$I_{t_j}^{f_i} = \prod_{j=1,2,\dots,n_t}^{i=1,2,\dots,n_f} f_i \quad (9)$$

where: $n_f = \#$ from variables
 $n_t = \#$ to variables

Note that Data Frame I is a symmetric data frame, with variables alphabetically listed for the “from” rows and “to” columns. The cells are marked with a “1” to indicate an interaction between the associated pair of variables is allowed. Otherwise, “0” indicates that no interaction is permitted. For a second-degree interaction, this is relatively simple, with only one interaction possible. With a third-degree regression, we have three pair interactions between all three variables, where every pair of interactions must be allowed to generate the three variable interaction term (or variable).

◇ **Aggregations**

$$A_{v_j}^{v_i} = \prod_{j=1,2,\dots,n_v}^{i=1,2,\dots,n_v} v_i \quad (10)$$

where: $n_v = \#$ of variables

7 The RCA Sales Grid

Keep in mind that the RCA protocol requires an R or Python program that can access R/earth and perform all of the detailed steps. It is data intensive and the work could not possibly be done manually. At the same time, assuming the program is bug free, you need a software program to ensure that the required work is done precisely and without human error.

It is also a necessity for VE's who do this work to be able to modify such programs as needed, especially when they are dealing with new unforeseen market areas, neighborhoods, properties or other new requirements or problems.

Within RCA processing we have three types of Sales Grids:

1. The RCA Processing Sales Grid, labeled in this paper as “MLSDData,” which is a very large data frame and associated spreadsheet that may contain many intermediate details that eventually go through an aggregation process, to arrive at the RCA Sales Grid mentioned below. An example would be too large to display here. Most likely valuation engineers will tailor this spreadsheet to their preferences. I intend to write a separate paper on developing such a grid at some future date.
2. The RCA Final Sales Grid which is used in non-GSE reports that looks something like [Table 2](#). This does mimic for example Fannie Mae's form, enough to provide some base of familiarity to the reader. However, notice that it carries more columns per sales comparable than the Fannie Mae grid: each comparable has a “Value Contribution” column alongside its “Measure” and “Adjustment” columns, and the subject has one as well — columns the Fannie Mae form lacks. A simpler form is also the [Table 1](#).
3. The GSE Upload Sales Grid that is used to upload the Sales Grid into software such as Alamode. Note however, that not all appraisal form software packages provide the ability to upload sales grid data from a spreadsheet. Out of necessity, such grids cannot include a separate column for valuation contributions, of which the GSEs like Fannie Mae have no comprehension. The strategy is to give them their required form, but back it up with an RCA Sales Grid, as well as other supporting documentation such as details on any variable aggregations.

The RCA Processing Sales Grids do not look like Fannie Mae Sales Grids but are, roughly, a transpose of the Fannie Mae Sales Grid, with rows and columns switched: Each row contains data for some property, and each column contains data for some property variable. There can easily be hundreds or thousands of property rows and 200 or more columns. The first row is reserved for variable names, and the second for a subject property, even if we are only doing a market analysis. When the spreadsheet is read into a data frame, then the first row of the sheet becomes the names attribute, and the second row for the subject property becomes the first row of the data frame.

The columns in the RCA Sales Grid include identification columns, then primary, external, and synthetic variables combined and fed as the independent variables into MARS. MARS outputs from these variables those that it thinks have a significant impact on the Sale Price, also known as the dependent or target variable. In second-degree regression, we may get pairs of these variables that act as new variables. With third-degree regression, we may also get variable triplets that act as so-called independent variables, although they are, of course, highly correlated with the underlying variables.

Table 1: Sample RCA Spreadsheet: Vertical Layout

Subject		Comp 1			Comp 2			
	Measure	Value Contribution	Measure	Value Contribution	Adjustment	Measure	Value Contribution	Adjustment
Sale Price			\$1,150,000			\$1,500,000		
Base Value		\$500,000		\$500,000	\$0.00		\$500,000	\$0
		Measured Features						
Living Area	1,530	\$463,500	1,350	\$382,500	\$81,000	1,700	\$540,000	-\$76,500
Lot Size	6,000	\$200,000	6,500	\$220,000	-\$20,000	7,000	\$240,000	-\$40,000
Age	53	\$63,600	57	\$68,400	-\$4,800	51	\$61,200	\$2,400
Bathrooms	2	\$15,000	3	\$30,000	-\$15,000	3	\$30,000	-\$15,000
Bedrooms	3	\$6,000	4	\$9,000	-\$3,000	4	\$9,000	-\$3,000
Total Measured		\$1,248,100.00		\$1,209,900.00	\$38,200		\$1,380,200.00	-\$132,100
		Residual Features						
Residual	CQA 5.8	\$30,000	CQA 2.5	-\$59,900	\$89,900	CQA 8.2	\$119,800	-\$89,800
		Residual Breakdown						
Design		7,000		-\$15,000	\$22,000		\$35,000	-\$28,000
Condition		5,000		-\$8,000	\$13,000		\$20,000	-\$15,000
Quality		8,000		-\$10,000	\$18,000		\$30,000	-\$22,000
Func Utility		5,000		-\$12,000	\$17,000		\$15,000	-\$10,000
Amenities		5,000		-\$14,900	\$19,900		\$19,800	-\$14,800
Sub-Total		30,000		-\$59,900	\$89,900		119,800	-\$89,800
Total			Total			Total		
Tot Value Contribution		\$1,278,100.00		\$1,150,000.00			\$1,500,000.00	
Adjusted Sale Price				\$1,278,100.00				\$1,278,100.00

8 Variables

On the input side of running MARS, we have only simple variables which are:

1. Property features loaded from the MLS spreadsheet.
2. Derived variables created by the VE to refine the MLS variables or add transformations of existing variables. For example, the VE may prefer to transform Date of Sale into “DaysOffMarket” which is equal to the effective date of the appraisal minus the Date of Sale.
3. The VE may import data from 3rd party sources, such as mortgage interest rates. Or, if latitude, longitude or elevation data are missing from the MLS data, he may import it from other sources. These variables could be called “external variables.”

On the output side of MARS, we work with price model that is a combinations of terms that either:

1. Contain only one of the input variable and provide the equation for the value contribution of that variable. These are called first degree terms or (output) variables. The term itself is treated as a value contribution value and given a name.
2. Contain two of the input variables and are the equation for the value contribution of the interaction of the given two variables. These terms maybe called second degree terms or (output) variables.
3. Contain three of the input variables and are the equation for the value contribution of the interaction between the three variables. These terms may be called 3rd degree terms or (output) variables in this paper.

The output variables of MARS are then value contributions, including the residual value contribution. They are in turn treated as variables in Sales Grid calculations, such as calculating adjustments or creating graphs.

We can have different types of variables that fall into two basic ontologies: (1) Variable Origin and (2) Variable Application, i.e. Non-residual vs Residual

8.1 Variable Origin Ontology

1. First Degree Variables
 - 1.1 MLS Regression Variables
 - 1.2 External Regression Variables
 - 1.3 Derived Regression Variables
2. Factor Variables:

To handle factor variables, a function is needed that can identify them. Since they are specified in the Excel project configuration workbook, a function is created that returns true if a variable passed to it has been classified as a factor type.
3. Interaction Variables: These are created by MARS in generating the model, if the degree is set to 2 or higher. However, 3 interacting variables is the most that could be recommended due to the difficulty of interpretation, the probability of overfitting and the impact on Degrees of Freedom and the resultant increase in property records to ensure a robust model.

- 3.1 Second Degree Variables: These are common and a good example would be GLA:BathRms, GLA:LotSize, DateOfSale:BathRms, Latitude _Longitude.
 - 3.2 Third Degree Variables: Less common interactions that suggest caution and possible over-fitting.
4. Residual Breakdown Variables

8.2 Variable Application Ontology

1. MARS Generated Value Contributions
 - 1.1 First Degree Variables
 - 1.1.1. MLS Regression Variables
 - 1.1.2. External Regression Variables
 - 1.1.3. Derived Regression Variables
 - 1.2 Interaction Variables
 - 1.2.1. Second Degree Variables
 - 1.2.2. Third Degree Variables
 - 1.3 Residual Breakdown Variables
 - 1.4 Aggregation Variables
2. Engineer Generated Variables & Values
 - 2.1 Residual Breakdown Variables
 - 2.1.1. Design/Aesthetics
 - 2.1.2. Landscape
 - 2.1.3. Functional Utility
 - 2.1.4. View
 - 2.1.5. Condition
 - 2.1.6. Quality
 - 2.1.7. ...

These variable groups will be given their notation and described in more detail in the next section

Protocol 3.1: Factor Variables

Factor variables, or simply factors, can occur in all terms, including interactions. They are important because they must be specially dealt with for MARS regression and graphing. While variables with character values are necessarily factors, numerical variables must be flagged as factor variables for MARS to recognize them as such. For example, MLS areas are often identified by number. In particular, the neighborhood areas in the San Francisco Bay Area are often identified with unique integers. If these values are passed to MARS as factors, then MARS will attempt to discover if certain areas have an average contributing value to property sales within their boundaries without regard to any relationship with other areas. In contrast, with normal variables, it will assume there is some kind of continuity in value contributions as the variable value changes. This is an important distinction. Furthermore, these factor variables can appear in model terms with non-factor variables, which makes graphing difficult. Specifically, when graphing single variable terms with factors, we lump all such factors together and simply draw a bar graph showing their contributions, positive or negative.

If the factors appear with other variables in terms, they will always appear with one possible value, because factor variables can have only one value for a given property: If an area has the value 662, by definition it can't have any other value for that area. If you find this confusing, to make matters worse, in the MARS-generated model, there is not a single variable name for the factor; MARS will take the root name of the factor variable it was given as input, then create new columns with variable names formed by appending the possible values. So, a single column in the Excel spreadsheet, such as *MlsArea*, will have multiple data frame columns created for each possible value, such as *MlsArea660*, *MlsArea661*, etc. A variable such as *MlsArea661* will have a value of 1 for properties in area 661; otherwise, 0. Then, MARS will regress on those columns as if they represented Boolean variables. These modified names will be used in the model provided by MARS. You will likely want to convert those model names back to their original name to make the graphs more understandable to clients who like it nice and simple (at least as simple as possible). Instead of seeing *MlsArea661*=1, we will see *MlsArea*=661. We then can graph terms by simply stating in the graph header something like "For MLS Area = 662". Thus, N degree terms with M factor variables are graphed as (N-M) degree terms, and the factor dimension disappears into the title.

Note that two or more factor variables could exist in a single term, so you would likely need a graph for each possible pair of values. If variable x with three distinct values and variable y with two distinct values appear in the same term with non-factor variable z, then you would need $2 \cdot 3 = 6$ graphs. An example would be "MlsArea" + "Architectural Style", e.g. Victorian homes in San Francisco might be worth more or less depending on the area of San Francisco they are in. Fortunately, in most areas, there are usually only 1-3 architectural styles important enough as value contributors to be used in the model (although there may be 6+ different architectural styles).

8.3 Second- and Third-Degree Terms

With second-degree or third-degree regression, some of terms in the output model, may include two or respectively three variables. For example:

$$\text{BathRms_GLA} = -52 * \max(0, 1200 - \text{GLA}) * \max(0, \text{BathRms} - 1)$$

Notice that we name these by alphabetically sorting the variable names and concatenating them,

perhaps with an underscore. We do the same with third degree terms on the variable name triples produced in the model. For example, “BathRms__GLA__LotSz.”

These variables get added to the primary input variables in Stage 3, when the RCA program calculates the contributions of all variables for each property, including the interaction variables.

8.3.1 Adjustment Variables

The RCA program will also calculate the adjustments for all variables and properties in Stage 3, after value contributions are calculated, by subtracting the corresponding comparable property value contribution for a feature from the subject contribution for that feature.

8.3.2 Aggregation Variables

Aggregation variables are defined to replace subsets of the variables, adding all their value contributions and adjustments into a common variable to be used in the report. For example, we may have split both finished and unfinished living area into finer detail variables:

1. Above Grade Legal Finished Area
2. Below Grade Legal Finished Area
3. Above Grade Illegal Finished Area
4. Below Grade Illegal Finished Area
5. Above Grade Unfinished Area
6. Below Grade Unfinished Area

Yes there are areas where this does make sense.

The MARS regression will regress on all of the variables and generate a model that will provide contributions and adjustments for them. But for a form report, these different contributions will probably have to be combined or aggregated into fewer variables. The details of the aggregation should be supplied in an addenda. A more frequent example, would be aggregating interaction adjustments into one of the primary variable adjustments. For example, we might aggregate the adjustment for GLA_LotSize to GLA or to LotSize, or even split them 50:50 between both, as determined by the Aggregation sheet.

8.3.3 Special Variables & Notation

π_i	Actual net sale price for property $i = 1, 2, \dots, n_p$; for the subject, π_0 denotes the value conclusion (see Proof I)
α_i	Adjusted net sale price for property $i = 1, 2, \dots, n_p$
ρ_i	MARS estimated net sale price for property $i = 0, 1, \dots, n_p$
β	Base value of the model
$\varphi_{i,j}$	Value contribution of regression variable $j = 1, 2, \dots, n_r$ for property $i = 0, 1, \dots, n_p$
$\delta_{i,j}$	Adjustment for regression variable $j = 1, 2, \dots, n_r$ for property $i = 1, 2, \dots, n_p$
ϵ_i	Total residual for property $i = 0, 1, \dots, n_p$
$\epsilon_{i,c}$	Residual component value contribution $c, c = 1, 2, \dots, n_c$ for property $i = 0, 1, \dots, n_p$
$\xi_{i,c}$	Adjustment for residual component $c, c = 1, 2, \dots, n_c$ for property $i = 0, 1, \dots, n_p$

where

$n_p = \#$ of comparable properties

$n_r = \#$ of regression variables

$n_c = \#$ of residual breakdown variables

8.3.4 Breaking Down Residuals

Once the MARS regression has created a model, it generates the estimated sale prices from the MARS-selected input variables. It subtracts that value from the corresponding Net Sale Price to get a residual value for each property. Now, the RCA protocol stipulates that once the VE has decided on the final property comparables, usually 6-12 property listings, he needs to go through each property listing and break down the calculated residual into the most likely features (latent variables) he thinks impact value, ignoring the possibility of random data errors. He might, for example, have these breakdown variables for a given property:

1. Design
2. Functional Utility

3. Over/Under Market Sale
4. Condition
5. Quality

Different properties will likely have some different residual breakdown variables, which need to be collected in one ordered set.

Estimating rare-feature contributions. Some value-bearing features are too rare for the regression channel: a workshop present in 3 of 780 sales cannot earn a defensible coefficient, and the forward pass will usually pass over such a variable entirely. These are residual features, and their contributions can be estimated *in residual space*: fit the model without the feature, then regress the model residuals on the excluded column(s) by ordinary least squares. For a binary flag the coefficient is a lump-sum contribution (equivalently, the mean residual offset of the flagged sales); for a numeric column it is a per-unit contribution. When several correlated amenities are estimated *jointly* (e.g. outbuilding square footage together with a workshop flag), the regression splits the credit between them rather than double-counting the same dollars in two breakdown rows. Estimates supported by fewer than about ten observations are indicative only and should be corroborated by depreciated cost or a widened sample (e.g. flags recovered from public remarks); the residual constraint itself caps whatever value is finally assigned. earthUI (v0.11+) implements this method directly as the *Residual Contribution* tab, including the joint estimation, per-sale residual evidence, and a documentation note for the workfile.

Notation: We use the notation in the above table to arrive at:

$$\epsilon_i = \epsilon_{i,1} + \epsilon_{i,2} + \dots + \epsilon_{i,n_c} \quad (11)$$

where n_c is the number of residual breakdown components.

The VE must use his judgment to break down the residual into the given components. One might think this would allow bias to enter the final value conclusion. However, that is not the case because we have mathematical proof that if the breakdown adjustments total the residual, they will not impact the value conclusion. The purpose of the breakdown is not to establish value, but to explain why the residual is what it is in comparison to other property sale residuals. The only spot where the engineer's bias can impact the final value conclusion is the estimate of the residual for the subject since, of course, there is no actual sale price for the subject needed to calculate a residual for it.

Each property has its set of residual value contributions, but these need to be merged into one set C over all properties:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Letting: } A_i &= \{\{\epsilon_{i,c}\}_{c=1}^{n_c}\} \\ C &= \{x \mid x \in \bigcup_{i=0}^{n_p} A_i\} \end{aligned}$$

where $[\epsilon_{i,c}]$ is the variable name for the value $\epsilon_{i,c}$ and A_i is the set of such variables and n_c is the number of values in each ϵ_i .

So, with the subject and comparable property data in separate columns, then under all the regression model variable value contributions for each property, we should see the set C of n_c corresponding residual value contributions.

9 Core RCA Proofs

Let:

$$\begin{aligned} n_p &= \# \text{ of properties} \\ n_r &= \# \text{ of regression variables} \\ n_c &= \# \text{ of residual component variables} \end{aligned}$$

Proof I: Each and every comparable adjusted sale price equals the estimated subject sale price.

For any comparable i , the adjusted sale price α_i is the sum of the net sale price π_i plus the adjustments: the differences between the subject and comparable value contributions for the base value, the regression variables $j = 1, 2, \dots, n_r$, and the residual. For the subject property, which has no actual sale, the net sale price π_0 is defined as the value conclusion $\beta + \varphi_{0,1} + \varphi_{0,2} + \dots + \varphi_{0,n_r} + \epsilon_0$. Then:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_i &= \pi_i + (\beta - \beta) + (\varphi_{0,1} - \varphi_{i,1}) \\ &\quad + (\varphi_{0,2} - \varphi_{i,2}) + \dots + \\ &\quad (\varphi_{0,n_r} - \varphi_{i,n_r}) \\ &\quad + (\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_i) \\ &= \pi_i + (\beta + \varphi_{0,1} + \varphi_{0,2} + \dots \\ &\quad + \varphi_{0,n_r} + \epsilon_0) \\ &\quad - (\beta + \varphi_{i,1} + \varphi_{i,2} + \dots + \\ &\quad \varphi_{i,n_r} + \epsilon_i) \\ &= \pi_i + \pi_0 - \pi_i \\ &= \pi_0 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Proof II: Altering the residual breakdown under the constraint that all residual component value contributions sum to the comparable residual, has no impact on the final value conclusion of the RCA protocol.

This is almost trivial. Yet without thinking about the math, it is easy to overlook this because traditional appraisers focus on the adjustments rather than the value contributions. It is the value contributions that cancel out here — a decades-long oversight. For some comparable k , $k > 0$, the total residual adjustment is equal to the sum of the n_c breakdown residual components which in turn is equal to the sum of the differences of value contributions, which is equal to the subject total residual minus the comparable total residual. And this is independent of the number of residual components created or what they represent. As long as the value of the residual components equals the total residual for both the subject and chosen comparable, ξ_k will not change.

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_k &= \xi_{k,1} + \xi_{k,2} + \dots + \xi_{k,n_c} \\ &= (\epsilon_{0,1} - \epsilon_{k,1}) + (\epsilon_{0,2} - \epsilon_{k,2}) + \dots + \\ &\quad (\epsilon_{0,n_c} - \epsilon_{k,n_c}) \\ &= (\epsilon_{0,1} + \epsilon_{0,2} + \dots + \epsilon_{0,n_c}) - \\ &\quad (\epsilon_{k,1} + \epsilon_{k,2} + \dots + \epsilon_{k,n_c}) \\ &= \epsilon_0 - \epsilon_k \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

10 MARS Model

10.1 Model Variable and Interaction “ g ” Functions

A core principle of the RCA method, is that “explanatory reasoning” is of utmost importance, Unfortunately providing meaningful graphs for the various value contribution equations, especially when interactions and factor variables are used, can be challenging. It is therefore considered imperative to provide a clear and strict protocol for creating these graphs. This is done herewith, but understand the protocol is aimed at the developer who is writing the R or Python code to generate the graphs, and might be only superficially of interest to those not involved with the coding.

The MARS-generated price model is a sum of a base constant plus additional terms, each involving 1 to 3 variables. To analyze it, we first split the model into individual terms. Then, multiple terms sharing the same set of variables, representing a single interaction, are combined into single interaction expressions. Assume the maximum degree of regression is 3. Consider a third-degree regression model consisting of a base constant, n_1 first-degree expressions, n_2 second-degree interaction expressions, and n_3 third-degree interaction expressions. This gives us four distinct groups of expressions, which are either single variable or multiple variable interactions, each graphed differently based on two factors: (1) whether they include a factor variable (a categorical variable), and (2) the number of unique variables they contain. Specifically:

- First-degree expressions (1 variable) are graphed in 2D.
- Second-degree expressions (2 variables) are graphed in 3D.
- Third-degree expressions (3 variables) are graphed as a *set* of 3D graphs.
- If an expression contains a factor variable, each unique factor reduces the graph’s dimensionality by one (e.g., a 3D graph becomes 2D if one variable is a factor).

The indexing of each function g provides the information needed to determine how it should be graphed, reflecting the number of unique variables and the presence of factor variables.

10.2 Indexing of the g Functions

Each function g is indexed as $f_{j,k} g_k^j$, where:

- $f_{j,k}$ is the first index (a superscript before g):
 - j ranges from 0 to 3 and identifies the group:
 - * $j = 0$: the base constant (an exception to the usual indexing).
 - * $j = 1$: first-degree expressions.
 - * $j = 2$: second-degree expressions.
 - * $j = 3$: third-degree expressions.
 - k is the index of a specific function within its group (e.g., $k = 1$ for the first function in group j).
 - The value of $f_{j,k}$ indicates the number of unique factor variables in the function:
 - * $f_{j,k} = 0$: no factor variables.
 - * $f_{j,k} > 0$: the number of factor variables (e.g., 1, 2, or 3).
- Trailing indices on g :

- The superscript j after g (e.g., g^j) repeats the group number for clarity.
- The subscript k after g (e.g., g_k) matches the k in $f_{j,k}$, identifying the function within its group.

While the indices of f and g align numerically, their roles differ: $f_{j,k}$ counts factor variables, which is critical for graphing decisions, while j and k on g define its group and position.

10.3 Graphing Dimensions

The dimension d of the graph for a function $f_{j,k} g_k^j$ is calculated as:

$$d = j - f_{j,k} \quad (14)$$

where:

- j is the number of unique variables (or group number, ignoring the constant case).
- $f_{j,k}$ is the number of factor variables.
- d is the number of continuous (non-factor) variables to be graphed, with a maximum of 3 (since the max degree is 3). A function with d continuous variables is drawn in $d + 1$ dimensions: $d = 1$ gives a 2D graph, $d = 2$ a 3D graph (or a 2D heat map), and $d = 3$ a set of 3D graphs.

For example:

- If $j = 3$ (3 variables) and $f_{j,k} = 0$ (no factor variables), then $d = 3 - 0 = 3$, requiring a set of 3D graphs, each fixing one of the variables.
- If $j = 3$ and $f_{j,k} = 1$ (one factor variable), then $d = 3 - 1 = 2$, requiring a 3D graph (or 2D heat map) for each value of the factor variable appearing in the model.
- If $j = 0$ (the constant), graphing isn't typically needed, as it's a single value.

When $d = 3$ (e.g., a third-degree expression with no factor variables), visualizing the full function may require multiple 3D graphs, each fixing one variable at different values to show a subset of the function's behavior.

10.4 The Final Model Equation

The MARS model is broken into four groups of expressions (constant, first-, second-, and third-degree). The indexing $f_{j,k} g_k^j$ tells us:

- j : the group and number of variables.
- $f_{j,k}$: the number of factor variables.
- $d = j - f_{j,k}$: the graph dimension.

This structure guides how each g function is visualized, ensuring the graphing method matches the expression's complexity and variable types.

The sale price estimate \hat{P} provided by the MARS model can be expressed as:

$$\hat{P} = f_{0,1}g_1^0 + \sum_{q=1}^{n_1} f_{1,q}g_q^1(x_*)$$

$$+ \sum_{r=1}^{n_2} f_{2,r}g_r^2(x_*, y_*)$$

$$+ \sum_{s=1}^{n_3} f_{3,s}g_s^3(x_*, y_*, z_*) \quad (15)$$

$n_1 = \#$ of first degree terms
 $n_2 = \#$ of second degree terms
 $n_3 = \#$ of third degree terms

10.5 Number of Charts Needed to Graph a Model

How many graphs are required to visualize all functions in a model? The answer depends on the variables, their interactions, and whether they are factor or non-factor variables.

The VE can limit variables and interactions in the Excel configuration file for R/earth, influencing which interactions are allowed. A practical approach is to let R/earth evaluate all possible interactions and select those with significant contributions to the sale price estimate, while checking for issues like over-fitting or collinearity. Some interactions may be disallowed, affecting higher-degree interactions (e.g., if a pair is excluded in a third-degree interaction, the entire combination is excluded).

For factor variables (e.g., MLS Area with 12 values interacting with GLA), graphing becomes more complex. This could require 12 graphs—one per area. If another factor like Architectural Style (6 values) interacts with MLS Area and GLA, up to $12 \cdot 6 = 60$ graphs might be needed. However, R/earth rarely finds all combinations significant; typically, only a few key interactions (e.g., specific areas and styles) warrant graphing, as identified by the model.

Here's a simplified guide to the number of graphs needed:

1. **Single-variable functions (non-factor):** 1 graph.
2. **Single-variable functions (factor):** 1 bar graph combining all factor values.
3. **Base function:** No graph needed.
4. **2nd-degree interactions (no factors):** 1 graph (e.g., 2D heat map with colors for sale price).
5. **2nd-degree interactions (1 factor):** 1 graph per factor value in the model (e.g., 2 values = 2 graphs).
6. **2nd-degree interactions (2 factors):** 1 graph with a matrix of factor combinations (e.g., 3 areas \times 2 styles = 6 cells).
7. **3rd-degree interactions (no factors):** Multiple graphs (e.g., 4 graphs for Bath count = 1, 2, 3, 4).
8. **3rd-degree interactions (1 factor):** 1 graph per factor value in the model.
9. **3rd-degree interactions (2 factors):** 1 graph per combination of factor values in the model.
10. **3rd-degree interactions (3 factors):** 1 graph per value of the factor with the fewest distinct values, using a color matrix for the other two.

More complex scenarios may require advanced graphing techniques.

There are other possibilities with likely more sophisticated graphs.

An example of a complete model generated by MARS is in [Figure 1](#).

Figure 1: MARS Model Components

Basis	$g_1^0 = 4957150$
Age	$g_1^1 = -3163.1809255 \cdot \text{Age}$
AreaNbr	$g_2^1 = -623197.75104 \cdot I\{\text{AreaNbr} = 471\}$
Baths	$g_3^1 = -111023.51496 \cdot \max(0, 2 - \text{Baths}) + 96735.52418 \cdot \max(0, \text{Baths} - 2)$
Beds	$g_4^1 = -233489.66415 \cdot \max(0, \text{Beds} - 5)$
DaysOffMkt	$g_5^1 = -2577.2188622 \cdot \max(0, 189 - \text{DaysOffMkt}) - 1282.8789534 \cdot \max(0, \text{DaysOffMkt} - 189)$
GLA	$g_6^1 = -666.73587914 \cdot \max(0, 4027 - \text{GLA}) + 281.36312913 \cdot \max(0, \text{GLA} - 4027)$
Latitude	$g_7^1 = -18141680.417 \cdot \max(0, \text{Latitude} - 37.573)$
LotSize	$g_8^1 = -85.005683404 \cdot \max(0, 8000 - \text{LotSize}) - 23.562970183 \cdot \max(0, \text{LotSize} - 8000)$
Age_Baths	$g_1^2 = -3916.3594872 \cdot \text{Age} \cdot \max(0, \text{Baths} - 3.5)$
Age_Garage	$g_2^2 = -6503.1897339 \cdot \text{Age} \cdot \max(0, \text{Garage} - 2)$
AreaNbr_LotSize	$g_3^2 = 78.54207825 \cdot I\{\text{AreaNbr} = 463\} \cdot \max(0, 8000 - \text{LotSize})$ $+ 87.263298012 \cdot I\{\text{AreaNbr} = 466\} \cdot \max(0, \text{LotSize} - 8000)$
AreaNbr_Baths	$g_4^2 = -1070222.5995 \cdot I\{\text{AreaNbr} = 464\} \cdot \max(0, \text{Baths} - 2)$
AreaNbr_Latitude	$g_5^2 = 17571072.548 \cdot I\{\text{AreaNbr} = 466\} \cdot \max(0, \text{Latitude} - 37.573)$
AreaNbr_GLA	$g_6^2 = -328.79173933 \cdot I\{\text{AreaNbr} = 471\} \cdot \max(0, \text{GLA} - 2550)$ $+ 525.69503229 \cdot I\{\text{AreaNbr} = 471\} \cdot \max(0, 2550 - \text{GLA})$
DaysOffMkt_GLA	$g_7^2 = 0.43839582286 \cdot \max(0, \text{DaysOffMkt} - 661) \cdot \max(0, 4027 - \text{GLA})$
FrPlcNbr_LotSize	$g_8^2 = 22.059059591 \cdot \max(0, 2 - \text{FrPlcNbr}) \cdot \max(0, \text{LotSize} - 8000)$ $+ 39.084508159 \cdot \max(0, \text{FrPlcNbr} - 2) \cdot \max(0, \text{LotSize} - 8000)$
GLA_LotSize	$g_9^2 = -0.45274160024 \cdot \max(0, \text{GLA} - 2994) \cdot \max(0, 8000 - \text{LotSize})$
ADU_Age_Garage	$g_1^3 = -5.4578633919 \cdot \max(0, \text{ADU} - 0) \cdot \text{Age} \cdot \max(0, 2 - \text{Garage})$
AreaNbr_Baths_LotSize	$g_2^3 = 60.607126605 \cdot I\{\text{AreaNbr} = 460\} \cdot \max(0, \text{Baths} - 2) \cdot \max(0, \text{LotSize} - 2480)$
AreaNbr_Baths_FrPlcNbr	$g_3^3 = 593779.41722 \cdot I\{\text{AreaNbr} = 464\} \cdot \max(0, \text{Baths} - 2) \cdot \max(0, \text{FrPlcNbr} - 0)$
AreaNbr_GLA_Latitude	$g_4^3 = 54199.925713 \cdot I\{\text{AreaNbr} = 464\} \cdot \max(0, \text{GLA} - 2670) \cdot \max(0, \text{Latitude} - 37.573)$ $+ 58934.565747 \cdot I\{\text{AreaNbr} = 471\} \cdot \max(0, \text{GLA} - 2550) \cdot \max(0, \text{Latitude} - 37.568)$
AreaNbr_DaysOffMkt_GLA	$g_5^3 = 0.37173306643 \cdot I\{\text{AreaNbr} = 470\} \cdot \max(0, 661 - \text{DaysOffMkt}) \cdot \max(0, 4027 - \text{GLA})$
Beds_GLA_LotSize	$g_6^3 = -5.1607264026 \cdot \max(0, 4 - \text{Beds}) \cdot \max(0, \text{GLA} - 2994) \cdot \max(0, 8000 - \text{LotSize})$
Age_AreaNbr_Baths	$g_7^3 = -10759.444688 \cdot \text{Age} \cdot I\{\text{AreaNbr} = 460\} \cdot \max(0, \text{Baths} - 3.5)$

11 Data Characteristics

The following section discusses MARS. MARS is entirely dependent on the data it receives, and most of this data will come from some MLS (Multiple Listing Service) or tax assessors. However, it may be routed through other data providers who maintain and improve data and then sell at some profit. In some areas, it is fairly reliable; in others, it is not so reliable. In critical instances, the property inspector has to make his observations and measurements, and their accuracy can be questioned.

The valuation engineer needs to understand what the data represents and how good of a job it does representing what it is supposed to represent. This invites a whole list of issues:

- How do you classify a variable as being a measurement?
- If a variable is not a measurement, what else can it be?
- How can regression be useful if the data it receives is not accurate?

Most of the data we get from MLS listing services and tax assessor data for regression is numerical data that implies measurements or counts. Some of it is logical, True or False.

11.1 Purpose of the Residual

The residual serves as an indirect gauge of the value added by variables not included in the regression model. In the language of the hedonic literature, these unmeasured features are *latent variables*: variables that influence sale price but are not measured directly, in most cases because there is no practical way to measure them objectively. Their values must instead be inferred, and in practice a latent variable value is often estimated through subjective judgment — in RCA, judgment anchored by the residual ranking. By ordering properties based on their residual or residual per square foot, we achieve an objective ranking from properties with the least appeal to those with the most. This ranking method is effective, provided a skilled analyst with a deep understanding of the local market crafts the MARS (Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines) model. The following are some additional requirements:

- **Quality of Data and Model:** A well-constructed regression model and high-quality data are prerequisites for reliable residuals. In the San Francisco Bay Area, my goal is to develop a model with an R2 of approximately 75-80% and a cross-validation R2 (CV R2) of 55-70%.
- **Avoid Over-fitting, Limit the R2:** The valuation engineer should aim for a maximum R2 of about 80% in most mature markets in higher priced areas like the SF Bay Area because much of a residential property's competitive value lies in its subjective appeal, which isn't quantifiable and thus can't be directly included in regression models. An R2 significantly above 80% might indicate an over-fitted model, prompting further scrutiny. Yet a word of caution: there are market areas with R2 values above 90% without over-fitting and there are difficult to appraise areas, where the best you might do is 50-60% or lower.
- **High R2 in Specific Areas:** However, there are regions, like subdivisions or other uniform residential areas, where higher R2 values are surprisingly common due to the homogeneity of the properties.

11.2 Condition and Quality Ratings as Approximate Regressors

Fannie Mae's condition and quality rating scales (C1–C6 and Q1–Q6) deserve special comment. These scales are too crude to be treated as true measured features, and because they are assigned by the appraiser, they are in practice subjective ratings — latent variables in their own right. It is useful to distinguish two levels explicitly: the appraiser's crude rating used as a regressor, *condition-coarse-grain* (condition-1) and *quality-coarse-grain* (quality-1), versus the fine-grain latent variables recovered from the residual, *condition-fine-grain* (condition-2) and *quality-fine-grain* (quality-2). The VE may accept the appraiser's coarse-grain ratings as approximations and regress on them, obtaining approximate value contributions that are useful as initial value assignments for the fine-grain latent variables. Where this is done, the protocol is to subtract the regression-estimated value contributions of these two coarse-grain variables from the model estimate — moving them out of the measured attributes under the regression section of the sales grid — and add them back onto the residual. From there, they are subsequently removed from the residual and assigned to the corresponding fine-grain latent variables, `res_condition1` and `res_quality1`. Additional information extracted from the MLS public remarks (`public_remarks`) and related string lists is then used to make micro refinements to these latent variable values. The end result is that the fine-grain value contributions replace the coarse-grain value contributions: the crude ratings serve only as scaffolding for the approximate model, and the values ultimately reported for condition and quality are the fine-grain, residual-derived ones.

11.3 Data Errors

Based on social media comments, the California Multiple Listing Service (MLS) data is generally of higher quality than many other United States regions. Typically, MLS data should be expected to be of good quality in most mature metropolitan areas but poorer in rural areas.

While there are occasional errors in the data for various reasons, these errors should generally cancel each other out and have minimal impact on the averages used in price models if sufficient data exists.

However, systematic biases can occur in specific areas. For instance, consider a neighborhood where many homes were initially constructed with full second stories, but some buyers were given the option to remove second-floor rooms to create vaulted ceilings on one or more first-floor rooms, significantly reducing the gross living area (GLA). The changes were not subsequently updated in the assessor's records for one reason or another. Consequently, MLS might show 2,400 square feet when the measured value is only 2,000 square feet. In such scenarios, the MLS data should be corrected before performing MARS (Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines) regression. It is important to note that obtaining this information for comparables may require some investigative effort. Discrepancies should be noted for future reference.

Given the foregoing, it is reasonable to assume that in high-quality MLS areas, the errors that spill over into the residual are minimal compared to the impact of subjective and unmeasured features such as design, condition, and quality. This is an important consideration when estimating the accuracy of the RCA method. For example, if the R^2 value for a given market area is 80%, then approximately 20% of the price is attributed to the CQA residual. A $\pm 10\%$ error in placing the subject within the residual ranking therefore propagates to a $\pm 10\% \cdot 20\% = \pm 2\%$ error in the final value conclusion. This is how you improve accuracy! In many cases, accurate value estimates well below $\pm 1\%$ are possible.

Therefore, treating residuals as indirect indicators of the collective value of unmodeled variables in MARS regression is reasonable, provided that the valuation engineer has sufficient local market experience to identify where and why systemic measurement biases exist. This approach ensures

that the analysis accurately reflects actual property values, acknowledging the limitations and nuances of real estate data.

Worked Example: Measuring Unmeasured Drivers at Sea Ranch

When the achievable R^2 in a market area is lower than the market's apparent homogeneity would lead one to expect, the framework's response is to identify and measure the missing variable rather than to accept the limitation. The Sea Ranch community in Sonoma County illustrates this directly.

A concrete instance of the measure-don't-accept response. The Sea Ranch community in Sonoma County is a coastal development where distance to the ocean is a primary value driver: a home several hundred feet from the bluff commands a substantially different price from one a quarter-mile inland, holding other features constant. The MLS data for the community does not record ocean distance as a variable. An initial MARS model fit on the available MLS variables produced lower explanatory power than the market's apparent homogeneity should have supported, with a residual structure that did not sufficiently order properties by any feature visible in the data — a signal that an important driver was missing from the model rather than that the market was genuinely noisy.

The remedy was direct measurement. The author obtained a community map showing the property layout relative to the coastline and measured the ocean distance for several hundred homes. The measured distances were added as a variable to the MLS dataset and the MARS regression was rerun. The new variable was selected by the model as significant, the explanatory power increased substantially, and the residual ranking subsequently ordered properties by patterns consistent with the remaining subjective features — view, condition, quality — rather than by the latent ocean-distance signal that had previously contaminated it. Elevation has been addressed similarly in hillside neighborhoods where the MLS variable is missing or unreliable.

The methodological principle is general. When the achievable R^2 falls below what the market's apparent homogeneity should support, the first hypothesis is that an important variable is missing from the model, and the appropriate response is to identify what it is and to collect the measurements directly. Sources include community maps, GIS data, tax assessor records, building department records, satellite imagery, and field inspection. The cost of such measurement work is real but bounded; once the variable is collected for a given market area, it can be carried forward into future assignments in that area. RCA absorbs new variables cleanly because the framework is indifferent to which variables enter the MARS regression — the residual structure tells the VE whether the new variable captures real signal, and the value contributions adjust accordingly.

The alternative response — accepting a low R^2 and reporting wider error bands — is defensible when the missing drivers are genuinely unmeasurable (buyer-specific preferences, transient market sentiment, idiosyncratic transaction circumstances) but not when they are merely uncollected. The VE's first move on a weak model should be to ask whether the missing signal is the latter.

11.4 What Is Accuracy?

Perfect accuracy for a valuation requires:

1. **Conformity to Market Value:** The hypothetical sales transaction of the subject property adheres 100% to the given definition of Market Value
2. **Accurate and Robust Model Development:** A high-quality MARS model is developed with an R^2 of about 75-80% and a CVR^2 of roughly 55-70% depending on location.

3. Good Data Error Analysis: All likely data errors for measured variables are understood and contained, with little spill over into residuals.
4. Systemic Bias Accounting: Any systemic bias in the data should be accounted and adjusted for.
5. Residual Rank Analysis: Ensure that residual rank properties follow a reasonable pattern of features from lowest to highest rank. Anomalies such as probate sales, shorts, and auction sales should be investigated, explained, and potentially removed.
6. Subject Placement: With a thorough understanding of residual ranking, the subject property should be accurately positioned. A property with a significantly higher appeal and another with a significantly lower appeal should be identified, and the subject placed between them and scored. Then attempt to narrow the ranking between the higher and lower properties as much as possible.
7. Explanatory Reasoning: Never sacrifice explanatory reasoning for accuracy. The appraiser must be able to explain the differences in value between the subject and comparable properties, at least to someone with reasonable intelligence. For example, a good MARS model with an optimal R2 and CVR2 can be used to explain value contributions for measured features, while the breakdown of the residual by the valuation engineer can be used to explain the value contributions of other features.
8. Over-fitting: Avoid over-fitting models, by not using property features that can identify either individually or in combination one or several properties. In particular avoid using factor variables whose values can specify a small number of properties. A factor variable that identifies neighborhoods in sizable data sets is appropriate, but one that identifies properties with swimming pools in an area where very few swimming pools exist, must be used with caution. A feature that identifies unique properties such as exact GIS coordinates, parcel numbers or addresses, is absolutely not allowed.

If the regression R2 is 80%, we expect about 20% of the subject value to be due to the residual. Now, this is only approximate. We know from the CQA-Residual curve that most of the distribution of residuals is at the lower and higher extremes of CQA. Based on the CQA-Residual curve and the extreme slope for the low and high CQA values, we might expect a less accurate estimate of the residual in these areas. However, that is counterbalanced by the relative scarcity of properties in these areas and the greater difference in appeal we see between adjacent properties. So, while we might talk of the impact of a range of $\pm 5\%$ in the mid-range, at the extremes we would be more concerned with a somewhat narrower range of $\pm 2 - \pm 3\%$

Calculating the accuracy of the RCA is, in general, somewhat difficult because of the non-linearity of the CQA-Residual curve. But it is possible on a case by case basis, given you have a reasonable residual ranking. The range of CQA scores is 0.0 to 10.0. With a good MARS model, your residual ranking should show a clear pattern of least to highest appeal and you should not find it difficult to rate within $\pm 5\%$ of the total range or ± 0.5 for the CQA score. If you have 100 properties in the regression, then that would be ranking the subject property accurately within a group of 10 properties. So, referring to the Burlingame sales data in Table 3, let's calculate the approximate accuracy (or error) for a VE estimated CQA of 7.5, 5.1 and 1.9, where his value conclusion for the subject is \$3,000,000. Note that since Table 3 only has a sample of the several hundred properties used, you will need to interpolate the residual where necessary (assuming linearity). To be clear, we are assuming the VE is very sure in each case that his ranking of the subject is within a range of ± 5 properties in the residual ranking of only 100 properties.

CQA= 7.5 ±0.5					
CQA	Residual	Abs. Diff	Exp. Error	Hyp. Sale Price	Pct Error
8.00	\$257,112				
7.50	\$197,113	\$59,999			
7.00	\$154,615	\$42,498	±\$51,249	\$3,000,000	±1.71%

CQA=5.1 ±0.5					
CQA	Residual	Abs. Diff	Exp. Error	Hyp. Sale Price	Pct Error
5.60	\$50,911				
5.10	\$19,559	\$31,352			
4.60	-\$28,207	\$47,766	±\$39,559	\$3,000,000	±1.32%

CQA= 1.9 ±0.5					
CQA	Residual	Abs. Diff	Exp. Error	Hyp. Sale Price	Pct Error
2.40	-\$228,411				
1.90	-\$276,381	\$47,970			
1.40	-\$326,938	\$50,557	±\$49,264	\$3,000,000	±1.64%

Finally, the only objective way to verify accuracy is to establish a strict protocol (which this paper only partially hints at in broad strokes) and verify its adherence. This is necessary because actual sale prices can deviate from market value due to imperfections in the market. Comparing appraisals and subsequent sales can provide some indication of accuracy. However, the complexities and instability of the real estate market necessitate the expertise of appraisers or highly qualified valuation engineers to provide value estimates based on established standards and protocols. These should be stringent enough to ensure that competent valuation engineers will independently arrive at nearly the same value conclusion. This should be an achievable goal, in most cases where good data is available.

11.5 The Subject Property As An Anomaly

Since estimating the Market Value of a property requires analysis of recent sales transactions, it is fair to ask if recent sales transactions do a good job of representing the various features of an older subject property that lacks modernization and repairs. This is particularly true in the San Francisco Bay Area, where recent sales transactions typically are homes that have gone through updating to improve their price for sale. So, the average quality and condition of sales comparables are generally superior to older homes that have not been on the market for quite some time. This difference in value should be picked up by the estimate of the residual for the subject property, or in other words, it's CQA score. This is an important consideration with respect to data quality and accuracy in valuing the subject property.

11.6 The CVR2's Importance In Dealing With Unexpected Data

MARS regression is based on multiple iterations of R/earth applied to a randomly selected subset of properties, which typically comprises 80% to 90% of the MLS data set referred to as the training set. The remaining 10% - 20% of properties serve as the test set. In this phase, the MARS model is created from the training data set and then is used to predict the sale prices of properties in the test data set, which are then compared to the actual sale prices. This methodology has been recognized by data miners as the most effective strategy to develop a robust model capable of predicting the sale prices of properties not yet observed.

However, the primary utility of the CVR2 metric lies not in its reflection of the regression model's factual accuracy concerning actual market area sales, but rather in its optimization of the model's predictive capabilities regarding hypothetical property sales as of a specified effective date. These properties are not included in the training data set and may exhibit new or unexpected combinations of characteristics missing in both the training and test data set property data.

Given this context, how can we estimate the sale price of a property that hasn't been updated in the past 15 years, assuming it was listed, for example, one month prior to the effective appraisal date? A model that demonstrates a strong CVR2 is more likely to provide the most accurate estimate, rather than a model that has not gone through this repetitive cross validation. It's also vital that the data set includes a sufficient number of comparable properties with varying degrees of updates, repairs and modernization.

Ultimately, if we possess a robust model that accurately predicts the value contributions of various properties features in our data set of comparable properties, we can effectively place the new subject property within the model's ranking of these properties by residual. This placement allows us to assign an appropriate CQA score and residual to the property.

12 Residuals

As indicated by the name “Residual Constraint Approach,” residuals are central to this methodology. Here, residual refers to the difference between a property’s net sale price and the sale price predicted by regression analysis.

A positive residual suggests that the property sold for more than its estimated price, based on typical measurable attributes like gross living area (GLA) and lot size, implying it might have more appeal than average. A negative residual indicates the property sold for less, potentially suggesting less appeal or other uncaptured negative attributes.

Given that larger homes likely have larger residuals, we might use residual per square foot based on GLA for a more normalized comparison. A more in-depth discussion of this issue is reserved for another paper.

12.1 Ranking & Scoring

After creating the MARS (Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines) model for measured variables, residuals are computed for each property. These residuals represent the difference between the observed net sale prices and the sale prices predicted by the model. An additional column should be created for the Residual/SF, that is, the residual divided by the living area of the residence, with the understanding that generally, the residual for specific properties is more significant with the size of the living area. Other possible statistics may work better in some neighborhoods, but they are a subject for another time.

Assumption 7: “Ranking by Residual”

In this paper, references to “ranking by residual” should be taken to mean ranking by residual, by residual/SF, or ranking by some other function of residuals, as the valuation engineer deems most appropriate for the market area. The author’s experience in SF Bay Area indicates residual/SF is generally the most reliable, especially when dealing with a subject property that has an unusually small or large GLA (Gross Living Area).

Next, the properties are sorted by their residuals from the most negative to the most positive. A Condition-Quality-Appeal (CQA) score is then generated for each property, ranging from 0.0 to 10.0. This score is calculated as follows:

The CQA score corresponds to the percentile rank of a property’s residual among all properties. Specifically, the score is computed by determining the percentage of properties that have residuals lower than that of the given property and dividing that percentage by 10. For instance, if a property’s residual is higher than the residuals of 50% of properties, then its score would be 5.0.

Due to rounding, one property can receive a score of 10.0, representing the property with the highest residual. However, a perfect score of 10.0 is theoretically impossible because, logically, no property can have a residual higher than that of 100% of the properties, itself included. On the other hand, the lowest possible score of 0.0 is possible since at least one property has no other properties with lower residuals. Note that more than one property might have a score of 0.0 due to rounding if many properties are being compared.

Therefore, the CQA score provides an intuitive measure of how well a property’s attributes align with the model’s expectations, with higher scores indicating better alignment with the model’s predictions.

It is essential to acknowledge that the CQA score can only be considered an indirect indicator of a comparable property’s appeal when the sale conditions are commensurate with its market

value. The Valuation Engineer is responsible for ascertaining whether the residual value incorporates over- or under-market elements by providing a comprehensive explanation and thorough investigation of the sales transaction. While significant over- and under-market sales are not frequent, they can occur in circumstances such as forced sales, probate, incompetence, collusion, etc.

Table 3 presents a semi-realistic extract of MLS data, along with residuals and CQA scores, both in total and per square foot. The total number of properties analyzed in this study was approximately 600. It is noteworthy that several variables that were regressed are not displayed. In other words, the residuals presented are after the impact of other variables, such as the date of sale, has been considered by MARS regression.

Table 3: Sales Comparables Sorted By Residual

SalePrice	Estimated SP	Residual	CQA	Residual/SF	CQA SF	GLA	SaleDate
\$3,450,000	\$2,318,865	\$1,131,135	10	\$420.50	9.98	2,690	2021-04
\$4,360,757	\$3,399,922	\$960,835	9.9	\$290.28	9.82	3,310	2021-09
\$4,000,000	\$3,134,444	\$865,556	9.8	\$234.57	9.60	3,690	2020-11
\$5,850,000	\$5,150,966	\$699,034	9.7	\$109.91	8.35	6,360	2021-12
\$3,600,000	\$3,023,366	\$576,634	9.5	\$269.46	9.79	2,140	2022-06
\$4,425,000	\$3,987,873	\$437,127	9.2	\$127.44	8.68	3,430	2021-08
\$2,530,000	\$2,164,564	\$365,436	8.9	\$180.02	9.28	2,030	2019-12
\$4,250,000	\$3,884,719	\$365,281	8.8	\$87.18	7.91	4,190	2021-08
\$3,350,000	\$3,034,613	\$315,387	8.5	\$130.87	8.75	2,410	2021-09
\$3,800,000	\$3,522,028	\$277,972	8.2	\$77.43	7.72	3,590	2020-09
\$4,200,000	\$3,963,748	\$236,252	7.8	\$56.12	6.89	4,210	2021-01
\$2,900,000	\$2,702,887	\$197,113	7.5	\$89.19	7.92	2,210	2021-07
\$4,250,000	\$4,103,885	\$146,115	6.9	\$39.38	6.29	3,710	2022-08
\$5,000,000	\$4,864,958	\$135,042	6.8	\$28.25	5.85	4,780	2021-07
\$4,320,000	\$4,199,672	\$120,328	6.5	\$33.90	6.04	3,550	2022-07
\$2,600,000	\$2,479,904	\$120,096	6.5	\$60.96	7.00	1,970	2021-10
\$3,400,000	\$3,301,146	\$98,854	6.2	\$30.32	5.90	3,260	2021-06
\$2,000,000	\$1,901,987	\$98,013	6.2	\$73.14	7.54	1,340	2019-11
\$3,000,000	\$2,919,718	\$80,282	5.9	\$26.50	5.79	3,030	2020-05
\$6,750,000	\$6,699,089	\$50,911	5.6	\$7.75	5.20	6,570	2020-08
\$5,652,000	\$5,601,570	\$50,430	5.5	\$12.83	5.37	3,930	2022-05
\$2,600,000	\$2,579,082	\$20,918	5.2	\$10.51	5.33	1,990	2022-03
\$1,925,000	\$1,905,441	\$19,559	5.1	\$11.51	5.36	1,700	2021-01
\$3,200,000	\$3,209,500	-\$9,500	4.8	-\$3.21	4.88	2,960	2020-11
\$4,150,000	\$4,187,560	-\$37,560	4.5	-\$10.49	4.68	3,580	2021-04
\$2,700,000	\$2,776,510	-\$76,510	3.9	-\$23.61	4.14	3,240	2021-07
\$3,450,000	\$3,567,668	-\$117,668	3.4	-\$31.05	3.90	3,790	2020-09
\$1,975,000	\$2,109,255	-\$134,255	3.3	-\$55.48	3.24	2,420	2020-02
\$1,950,000	\$2,085,431	-\$135,431	3.2	-\$68.40	2.86	1,980	2021-02
\$3,695,000	\$3,859,154	-\$164,154	3.1	-\$47.04	3.56	3,490	2021-05
\$2,288,000	\$2,455,747	-\$167,747	2.9	-\$56.86	3.19	2,950	2020-06
\$2,635,000	\$2,802,781	-\$167,781	2.9	-\$56.87	3.18	2,950	2020-09
\$2,050,000	\$2,217,794	-\$167,794	2.9	-\$82.66	2.46	2,030	2021-07
\$1,550,000	\$1,731,804	-\$181,804	2.7	-\$130.79	1.32	1,390	2021-05
\$2,800,000	\$3,028,411	-\$228,411	2.4	-\$81.58	2.51	2,800	2021-02
\$3,700,000	\$3,976,381	-\$276,381	1.9	-\$76.99	2.62	3,590	2021-08
\$2,517,500	\$2,834,974	-\$317,474	1.5	-\$120.71	1.48	2,630	2019-11
\$2,550,000	\$2,905,330	-\$355,330	1.1	-\$115.74	1.64	3,070	2019-12
\$1,815,000	\$2,263,944	-\$448,944	0.7	-\$273.75	0.15	1,640	2021-11
\$3,711,000	\$4,683,454	-\$972,454	0	-\$226.68	0.37	4,290	2021-12
\$2,225,000	\$3,332,960	-\$1,107,960	0	-\$370.56	0.03	2,990	2021-08
\$3,550,000	\$4,746,489	-\$1,196,489	0	-\$274.42	0.14	4,360	2022-06

12.2 CQA-Residual Curve

A plot of the CQA vs. the Residual/SF for a neighborhood will invariably result in the CQA-Residual Characteristic Curve shown in [Figure 2](#). This particular plot represents data from Burlingame, CA, circa 2022. Similar curves are generally observed when plotting CQA scores against Residual values; however, I prefer using Residual/SF for its relevance in contextualizing the CQA with respect to the Gross Living Area (GLA) of the subject property. By multiplying the Residual/SF by the GLA, one can convert the CQA of a property into a corresponding residual value.

The valuation engineer must carefully evaluate whether the size of the property, specifically the Gross Living Area (GLA), significantly influences the magnitude of residuals. This assessment is critical because it can determine the most accurate method for calculating property values. For instance, high-end kitchen appliances and luxurious bathroom fixtures can substantially enhance a home's residual value. However, in neighborhoods where the size and layout of kitchens and bathrooms are generally uniform, these upgrades might not correlate strongly with the GLA. Their impact on the residual value may be less about the space they occupy and more about the quality they represent.

Conversely, expensive exterior features and materials, which notably improve a property's curb appeal, may have a more direct relationship with the property's size. Larger homes can accommodate more elaborate exteriors, such as extensive landscaping, superior roofing materials, or expansive patios, which naturally enhance the property's overall appeal and, consequently, its residual value.

Therefore, it is essential for valuation engineers to consider these dynamics when analyzing residuals. They should not only assess the intrinsic value added by high-quality fixtures and features but also understand how these enhancements interact with the property's physical dimensions. This comprehensive approach ensures that valuations accurately reflect both the qualitative and quantitative attributes of a property.

Consequently, it is recommended to plot both the CQA-Residual and CQA-Residual/SF foot curves and study the differences, which can indicate patterns in a market area. The valuation engineer can have his program compute both residuals and take some weighted average to calculate the residual to be assigned to the subject. It may or may not make much of a difference.

12.3 The CQA Curve Characteristics

The Condition-Quality-Appeal (CQA) curve offers a sophisticated model for understanding how property values fluctuate based on appeal, condition, and market dynamics within a given area. This model captures the interplay of economic and physical factors that influence the real estate market, reflecting nuanced realities of property valuation across different market segments.

12.3.1 Analysis of the CQA Curve Components

1. Exponential Decay on the Left Side of the Curve:

As the CQA score decreases from around 2 to 0, properties exhibit characteristics of rapid deterioration. This part of the curve is well-represented by an exponential decay function, emphasizing how quickly a property can lose its appeal and value without proper maintenance and updates. Physical degradation such as rotting wood, fading colors, and rusting metal accelerates this decline, particularly in homes that are not regularly maintained.

2. Linear Increase in the Middle Range:

The bulk of the market typically fits within this category, where the appeal increases almost linearly from scores of around 2 to 8. This section reflects properties that are generally maintained to standard but don't necessarily feature exceptional qualities or locations. It represents the broad middle class of housing, encompassing the majority of the housing market where homes are competitively priced based on their standard features and overall condition.

3. Exponential Growth on the Right Side of the Curve:

Here, the curve rises exponentially from scores 8 to 10, mirroring the higher appeal end of the market. Properties in this segment often belong to wealthier individuals who not only invest in superior maintenance but also in enhancements that significantly boost property appeal and value. The exponential growth reflects the scarcity of such high-quality properties and the high demand among affluent buyers. And understand, a lower priced home may rate very high in terms of appeal, while a large and expensive home may rate low. These dynamics are uncovered by expert use of MARS and usually go unnoticed by most appraisers.

12.3.2 Market Dynamics and Social Implications

The CQA curve implicitly narrates the story of relative wealth and economic disparity within different regions. In places like San Mateo County, the variation in property values between areas like Burlingame and wealthier neighborhoods such as Hillsborough, Woodside, or Atherton illustrates significant socioeconomic divides. This disparity affects everything from property maintenance to market valuations and ultimately influences buyer demographics and real estate market trends.

Moreover, the anecdote about a relatively wealthy individual investing in a high-quality home within a mid-tier neighborhood they are comfortable with and where for various reasons they would prefer to live, underscores another critical aspect of real estate economics — the concept of “overbuilt” properties. Such properties, while very appealing, may not find local buyers able to pay the price they might have fetched in a higher priced market area.

The CQA-Residual curve is characteristic to each market area, and should not be overlooked when doing your analysis.

12.4 Subject Residual

Unlike the comparables, the subject property does not possess an objectively determined residual; it must be estimated by the Valuation Engineer (VE). This estimation introduces a degree of subjectivity into the Residual Constraint Approach (RCA) protocol, marking a critical juncture where personal judgment plays a pivotal role.

To estimate the Condition-Quality-Appeal (CQA) score, the VE meticulously analyzes the ranked properties, searching for discernible patterns within the rankings. This analysis often involves a detailed review of MLS photos associated with each property. An exhaustive review is impractical for a large dataset, such as 600 properties. Instead, the VE applies practical reasoning to approximate the subject's likely position within the overall ranking. Properties requiring extensive repairs, or “fixers,” are generally positioned near the bottom, whereas those with superior updates and appeal tend to rank near the top.

The VE then adopts a more focused approach, 'jumping' within the ranking to identify comparables that closely match the subject's appeal. As the range narrows, the VE pays closer attention to similarities among the properties, particularly in aspects like quality, condition,

Figure 2: CQA-Residual Characteristic Function

design aesthetics (including elements like paint, woodwork, stonework, and windows), functional utility, and other relevant characteristics

It is crucial to understand that the VE's judgments are fundamentally guided by the market-established rankings. This ensures that the subjective elements of the process are anchored by market realities, striving for a fair and accurate valuation of the subject property.

12.5 RCA Value Conclusion

12.5.1 General Considerations

Determining a CQA score is pivotal for establishing the estimated residual value of a property, as these elements are intrinsically linked. While it is possible to assess a property without a CQA, this metric provides valuable context by illustrating where the property stands compared to others in the market area. For instance, a CQA score of 3.2 indicates that the property has greater appeal than 32% of comparable properties in the vicinity. If objections exist to the assigned score, disputants must consult the rankings and justify any proposed adjustments based on photographic evidence or other substantial data. If the ranking system is robust and the Valuation Engineer (VE) has accurately positioned the property within this framework, it is unlikely that significant discrepancies will arise.

In the reporting phase, typically, 6 to 12 recent and relevant sales comparables are selected to support the valuation conclusion. The differences between these comparables and the subject property are analyzed, with each variable being adjusted accordingly. These adjustments are then applied to the net sale prices of the comparables to derive adjusted sale prices. As demonstrated mathematically, these adjusted prices should converge with the estimated sale price of the subject property.

12.5.2 Review, Auditing, Complaints

Once the estimated residual for the subject property is determined, residual adjustments can be calculated for all comparables. These adjustments serve as constraints for further manual breakdowns by the VE, tailored to specific CQA variables deemed pertinent. It is important to emphasize that these detailed breakdowns are explanatory and do not influence the final valuation, as affirmed in Proof II.

Concerning complaints submitted by users not satisfied with the appraisal value conclusion, a traditional appraiser typically has to waste time explaining why this or that property with a higher or lower price does not have the user-expected impact on value. With RCA, all possible comparable sales (usually 100-600) are typically evaluated to precisely the same value as the price conclusion, so it takes little effort to show the adjustments for some arbitrary property. The entire RCA process is automated and objective, except for the scoring of the subject residual. And so another advantage of the RCA is that criticism for imperfections in the subjective judgment of the VE is mainly restricted to that one area - and it can be effectively and efficiently managed. Also, assuming an R2 of about 80%, the impact of a $\pm 10\%$ error in estimating the subject residual amounts to a $\pm 2\%$ error in the final value estimate.

In many cases, the subject fits so perfectly in the residual ranking of properties, that the accuracy can be expected to be within $\pm 1\%$.

The sum of the estimated residual and the subject's MARS estimated sale price yields the final value conclusion known as the Residual Constraint Approach (RCA) Value Conclusion. This process ensures a comprehensive and transparent approach to property valuation, fostering

confidence in the accuracy and fairness of the assessment.

13 Conclusion

The Residual Constraint Approach is a framework with three substantive contributions: a structural anti-anchoring property derived from fitting the model on the whole market rather than on a small comparable set (Proof I); an invariance result that allows residual breakdown to serve as an explanatory layer without disturbing the value conclusion (Proof II and the remark following it); and an empirical regularity — the CQA-Residual characteristic curve — that appears to recur across market areas in characteristic exponential-linear-exponential form. The framework’s limitations are equally substantive: the residual decomposition is invariant but not identifying, the CQA placement step relies on VE judgment that has not yet been validated through formal inter-rater study, and the accuracy claims await benchmarking against alternatives.

What this paper presents is a framework and a protocol. What it does not yet present, but the larger research program now in progress does, is an executable, audit-traceable pipeline that operationalizes the protocol in software with defensible defaults. That pipeline — the earthUI package on CRAN for the MARS basis-function stage, the glmnetUI package for the regularized structural model on those bases, and the mgcvUI package for spatial smoothing — is the subject of companion articles in this issue and is the bridge from RCA-as-method to RCA-as-deliverable. The doctrine-practice gap in appraisal regulation (Craytor, 2026, this issue) supplies the reason that bridge matters: appraisal outputs are economically consumed as forward-looking risk inputs, and a framework that makes the present-value opinion auditable and reproducible is a precondition for any honest engagement with that forward-looking use. RCA is one move in that larger project. It is not the whole project, and this paper does not claim it is.

References

- Ambrose, Brent W. et al. (2025). “Do Appraiser and Borrower Race Affect Mortgage Collateral Valuation?” In: *Review of Finance*. DOI: [10.1093/rof/rfaf046](https://doi.org/10.1093/rof/rfaf046).
- Craytor, William Bert (2026). “The Doctrine–Practice Gap in Real Estate Appraisal: A Structured Account of Functions, Boundaries, and Tensions”. In: *Valuation Engineer Journal* 1.1.
- Friedman, Jerome H. (1991). “Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines”. In: *The Annals of Statistics* 19.1, pp. 1–141.
- Hastie, Trevor, Robert Tibshirani, and Jerome H. Friedman (2017). *The Elements of Statistical Learning: Data Mining, Inference, and Prediction*. Second. Springer Series in Statistics. New York, NY: Springer. ISBN: 978-0-387-84857-0.
- James, Gareth et al. (2013). *An Introduction to Statistical Learning: With Applications in R*. Springer Texts in Statistics 103. New York: Springer. ISBN: 978-1-4614-7137-0.
- Krivorotov, George and Michael LaCour-Little (2020). “AVM versus Appraisal-Based Underwriting in Refinance Mortgages: The Trade-off Between Noise and Bias”. In: *SSRN Electronic Journal*. DOI: [10.2139/ssrn.3603327](https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3603327).
- Kuhn, Max and Kjell Johnson (2016). *Applied Predictive Modeling*. Corrected at 5th printing. New York: Springer. ISBN: 978-1-4614-6848-6.
- Milborrow, Stephen (2024a). *Earth: Multivariate Adaptive Regression Splines*. R Package. URL: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=earth>.
- (2024b). *Notes on the Earth Package*. Tech. rep. URL: <http://www.milbo.org/doc/earth-notes.pdf>.
- (2024c). *Variance Models in Earth*. Tech. rep. URL: <http://www.milbo.org/doc/earth-varmod.pdf>.

- Perry, Andre M., Jonathan Rothwell, and David Harshbarger (2018). *The Devaluation of Assets in Black Neighborhoods*. Tech. rep. Brookings Institution.
- Perry, Andre M., Jonathan Rothwell, J. Williamson, et al. (2024). *How Racial Bias in Appraisals Affects the Devaluation of Homes in Majority-Black Neighborhoods*. Tech. rep. Brookings Institution.
- Property Appraisal and Valuation Equity Task Force (2022). *Action Plan to Advance Property Appraisal and Valuation Equity*. Tech. rep. U.S. Department of Housing and Urban Development.
- Tzioumis, Konstantinos (2016). “Appraisers and Valuation Bias: An Empirical Analysis”. In: *Real Estate Economics* 45.3, pp. 679–712. DOI: [10.1111/1540-6229.12133](https://doi.org/10.1111/1540-6229.12133).
- Williamson, Jake and Mark Palim (2022). *Appraising the Appraisal: A Closer Look at Divergent Appraisal Values for Black and White Borrowers Refinancing Their Home*. Tech. rep. Fannie Mae.
- Zhang, Wengang (2020). *MARS Applications in Geotechnical Engineering Systems: Multi-Dimension with Big Data*. Singapore: Springer. ISBN: 978-981-13-7421-0.